

D11.4: ZeroW Impact Assessment

Disclaimer and acknowledgements

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101036388

Disclaimer

The content of this document reflects only the author's view. Neither the European Commission nor REA are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the ZEROW consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

Neither the ZEROW Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be responsible or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein.

Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the ZEROW Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information advice or inaccuracy or omission herein.

Copyright message

© ZEROW Consortium. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Acronym **ZeroW** **Grant Agreement No 101036388**

Full Title	Systemic Innovations Towards a Zero Food Waste Supply Chain - ZeroW		
Call	H2020-LC-GD-2020 Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: Research and innovation in support of the European Green Deal.		
Topic	LC-GD-6-1-2020	Type of action	IA
Project coordinator	Inlecom Commercial Pathways		
Project URL	http://www.zerow-project.eu/		
Deliverable	D11.4: ZeroW Impact Assessment		
Document Type	R	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead beneficiary	Inlecom Commercial Pathways (ICP)		
Responsible author	Anna George (ICP)		
Additional authors and contributors			
Due date of delivery	31/12/2025	Submission date	09/12/2025

Document information

Document history			
Issue	Date	Comment	Author
V0.1	30/01/23	Document structure created	AG
V0.1	28/03/2023	Introduction section and impact description sections - completed	AG
V0.1	30/06/2023	Impact assessment evolution sections started with RP1 progress update	AG
V0.1	20/06/2024	Update of section "objectives achievement" by M30	AG
V0.1	24/07/2024	Introduction section updated with links and inputs from other deliverables and WPs	AG
V0.2	30/09/2025	Document structure – updated. Methodology section - completed	AG
V0.2	15/10/2025	Impact achievement section – description of impacts mechanisms - completed	AG
V0.2	31/10/2025	Impact achievements values - added	AG
V0.2	14/11/2025	Post project impacts, gaps and opportunities and conclusion sections completed	AG
V1.0	09/12/2025	Comments addressed and document finalised	AG

Approved by:			
Issue	Date	Name	Organisation
V1.0	18/11/2025	Jenny Rainbird	ICP
V1.0	25/11/2025	Aristos Halatsis	VLTN
V1.0	27/11/2025	Chantal den Broeder	VLTN

Contents

1. Introduction	10
1.1 Food loss and waste challenge	10
1.2 ZeroW – Systemic Innovation Towards Zero Waste Food Supply Chain	12
1.2.1 Systemic approach to change	12
1.2.2 SILLs as systemic demonstrative environments	14
1.2.3 Systemic Innovation Readiness Level (SIRL) and learning loops	16
1.3 Addressing the GA requirements	17
1.4 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	19
1.5 Methodological overview	20
1.5.1 Impact assessment framework	20
1.5.2 Data sources and links with other WPs	21
1.5.3 Impact categories	23
1.5.4 Limitations, assumptions, and data boundaries	26
2. ZeroW impacts achievement	27
2.1 Reduction of Food Loss and Waste Across the Food Supply Chain (in Impacts 1 and 3)	27
Post-harvest	27
Processing	30
Retail	33
Consumption	38
2.2 Reduction of Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Emissions Related to FLW (Impact 2)	42
Post-harvest	43
Processing	44
Retail	45
Consumption	46
2.3 Reduction of Unsustainable Packaging (in Impact 3)	48
2.4 Provision of Sufficient, Safe, Nutritious, Healthy and Affordable Food (Impact 4)	52
Improved food availability in food banks due to reduced FLW	53
Improved food safety with minimal FLW with optimised and predictive control in food production	54
Longer shelf-life of products with smart packaging	55
Optimised nutritional diets with minimal FLW	55
2.5 Improved Overall Sustainability of Food Systems (Impact 5)	56
Carbon footprint of smart compostable packaging	57
Carbon footprint of food products for human consumption from valorisation of side streams, imperfect produce and post-harvest food loss	58
'Just' allocation of costs and benefits among food actors	59
Economic sustainability of ZeroW FLW solutions	68
Consumers benefitting from the project results	69
2.6 Improved Resilience of Food Systems to Shocks and Stresses (Impact 6)	70

2.7 Increased Awareness and Behavioural Change	72
3. Post project impacts	75
3.1 Achieving medium and long term FLW reduction	76
3.2 Achieving medium and long term GHG reduction	79
4. FLW prevention and reduction: identified challenges, barriers and gaps for further research	80
Technical aspects, digital tools, platforms and data spaces	80
Measurement, data quality and metrics	81
Economic incentives, regulation and governance.....	82
Behavioural and socio-cultural drivers of FLW.....	83
Social innovation and capacity	84
Business models and commercialisation of FLW innovations.....	84
5. Conclusions and recommendations	85
5.1 Overall impact and validation against Grant Agreement objectives	85
5.2 Systemic Innovation and Just Transition Reflections	90
5.3 Outlook: medium and long term impact potential (2030–2050 trajectory)....	91

List of figures

Figure 1 Food loss and waste in EU, data from Eurostat, Sept 2025	10
Figure 2 Lock-in effects contributing to food loss and waste	11
Figure 3 ZeroW at a glance	12
Figure 4 ZeroW approach	13
Figure 5 WP11 in the overall project structure. Tasks and deliverables.....	14
Figure 6 ZeroW impact assessment framework.....	20
Figure 7 Links and data inputs from the rest of the ZeroW work packages	21
Figure 8 Key ZeroW Expected Impacts	23
Figure 9 Links between ZeroW project’s objectives and expected impacts	25
Figure 10 Wasteless greenhouse solutions (SILL3)	27
Figure 11 Real time sensing and computer vision integration in SILL3.....	28
Figure 12 Flexible food valorisation as a service (SILL4)	28
Figure 13 “Ugly” food identification at post-harvest level (SILL5).....	29
Figure 14 Flexible, small scale processing (Sill4).....	30
Figure 15 Valorisation of class B and side streams (SILL4)	31
Figure 16 Data driven production process control (SILL6) – Use case 1 and 2	31
Figure 17 Data driven production process control (SILL6) – Use case 3.....	32
Figure 18 Innovative, sustainable and smart packaging (SILL2).....	33
Figure 19 For accurate reading, the colour change can be read by a mobile app ..	34
Figure 20 Objective quality identification at retail level (SILL5).....	35
Figure 21 “De-wasting” on retail level through efficient redistribution (SILL7)	36
Figure 22 Retail FW valorisation through microalgae production (SILL8)	37

Figure 23 Prototype of the smart packaging, integrating biodegradable barrier for shelf life extension and smart, colour changing indicator for the freshness status of the fish (SILL2) 39

Figure 24 EU food emissions slowly fall, but their share of EU total rises, (Source: European Centre for Development Policy Management (ECDPM), How the EU’s vision for agriculture and food could shape global food security and climate-change) 42

Figure 25 Compostable tray made of biobased materials 49

Figure 26 Industrial compostability tests: tray 50

Figure 27 Permeable barrier in ZeroW SILL2 packaging solution 51

Figure 28 Biobased lid..... 51

Figure 29 Industrial compostability test: top lid film..... 51

Figure 30 Smart freshness label 52

Figure 31 FLW score labels: strict, relative and balance versions 66

Figure 32 NUTS-3 regions reached by the SILLs activities 74

Figure 33 ZeroW policy briefs..... 78

Figure 34 Achieved key impacts..... 85

Figure 35 ZeroW innovations impacts contribution towards F2F Strategy pillars... 91

List of tables

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used 8

Table 2 Food loss and waste lock in effects and ZeroW technical innovations addressing them 15

Table 3 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description 17

Table 4 Final proposal for just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets (2030) as per D8.2 77

Table 5 Grant Agreement impact targets achievement..... 88

Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
DSS	Decision Support System
EC	European Commission
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EU	European Union
F2F	Farm to Fork
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FSC	Food Supply Chain
FW	Food Waste (used in some sections as shorthand)
GA	Grant Agreement
GD	Green Deal
GEA	Greenhouse Environmental Automation (contextual technical term in D11.4)
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
MAGNET	Modular Applied General Equilibrium Tool
MC	Monte Carlo (used in LCA uncertainty analysis)
NIR	Near Infrared (spectroscopy)
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
REA	Research Executive Agency
SILL	Systemic Innovation Living Lab
SIRL	Systemic Innovation Readiness Level
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VAT	Value Added Tax
WFD	Waste Framework Directive
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Deliverable D11.4 provides the overall impact assessment of ZeroW. Its purpose is to consolidate all validated evidence generated across the project and assess the extent to which the nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) have achieved the impacts set out in the Grant Agreement (GA). Task 11.4 brings together results from all the work packages (WP) within the project and applies the integrated assessment framework established in D5.1. The deliverable evaluates project performance across the seven expected impacts and situates the findings within the wider objectives of the Farm to Fork Strategy and the European Green Deal.

Main achievements

The assessment confirms that ZeroW met or exceeded almost all impact targets. Across all supply chain stages, the demonstrated innovations achieved substantial reductions in FLW and associated GHG emissions, with results well above targets. All 2025 targets for decreasing non-recyclable and non-compostable packaging at retail and consumer levels were fully achieved. The project exceeded targets for food safety, food bank availability, shelf-life extension and nutritional optimisation. Carbon footprints from valorisation routes and compostable packaging decreased well beyond the expected thresholds, and the just-allocation criterion was achieved, with consumer reach far exceeding the target, contributing to the overall sustainability of food systems. Food system resilience improved tangibly across all stages, meeting the qualitative target of significant enhancement. ZeroW surpassed all outreach targets, reaching 1.84 million consumers and food actors across 151 NUTS 3 regions and involving 168 organisations.

Contributions to EU policy objectives

The findings confirm that the demonstrated innovations contribute directly to the Farm to Fork Strategy target and the EU targets for reducing food waste and related emissions. The evidence confirms that measures that prevent food loss and waste, along with valorisation pathways, remove a considerable portion of emissions that would otherwise arise in downstream stages such as transport, refrigeration and disposal. Results related to food safety, nutrition, affordability and enhanced availability in food banks align with the Farm to Fork ambitions for healthier and more sustainable diets. The achievement of all packaging-reduction targets supports the Green Deal transition to circular, resource-efficient packaging and reduced dependence on virgin materials..

Key policy-relevant messages

The assessment highlights that systemic innovations integrating diverse innovation dimensions across the food supply chain generate far greater climate and sustainability benefits than isolated innovations. It shows that avoided disposal-stage emissions are a major driver of GHG reductions, highlighting the importance of prioritising FLW prevention, reduction and valorisation in EU regulatory design. The findings also confirm that economic burden differences across actors, measured through the attributed costs and benefits of the innovations, remained below the 20 percent threshold, demonstrating compatibility with a fair and just transition, as framed in D8.2. These results provide concrete, quantified evidence that FLW-reduction solutions, such as those demonstrated in ZeroW, can support coherent EU policy action towards the Farm to Fork 2030 and Green Deal 2050 goals, particularly by addressing existing gaps and barriers and strengthening the enabling conditions and governance arrangements required across the food system.

1. Introduction

1.1 Food loss and waste challenge

Food Loss and Waste (FLW) is a significant global issue with far-reaching environmental, economic, and social consequences. Every year, approximately one-third of all food produced for human consumption is lost or wasted, leading to inefficiencies across the food supply chain. This wastage contributes to unnecessary greenhouse gas emissions, depletes resources such as water and land, and exacerbates food insecurity.

Figure 1 Food loss and waste in EU, data from Eurostat, Sept 2025

Food loss and waste (FLW) remains a critical challenge for the European Union, undermining the sustainability, resilience, and efficiency of its food systems. According to Eurostat's most recent estimates¹, the EU generated around 58 million tonnes of food waste in 2023, corresponding to approximately 130 kilograms per person. The

associated **economic cost** is estimated at over €130 billion per year, reflecting inefficiencies across all stages of the food supply chain²

More than half of all food waste in the EU occurs at the household level, although substantial quantities are also lost earlier in production and processing³:

- Primary production: 10%
- Processing and manufacturing: 18%
- Retail and distribution: 8%
- Food services: 11%
- Households: 53%

From an **environmental perspective**, food waste accounts for about 16% of the total greenhouse-gas emissions from the EU food system⁴. The European Environment Agency also notes that food waste places significant pressure on Europe's land, water and energy resources in addition to its contribution to GHG emissions⁵.

¹ Eurostat: [Food waste and food waste prevention - estimates](#)

² European Parliament: [Food waste in Europe: facts, EU policies and 2030 targets](#) (last updated 11/09/2025)

³ Eurostat: [Food waste and food waste prevention - estimates](#)

⁴ EC (2023) [Reducing Food Waste](#), Publications Office of the European Union, doi:10.2875/469411

⁵ EEA Report 02/2025, [Preventing waste in Europe – Progress and challenges, with a focus on food waste](#)

From a **social perspective**, Eurostat data indicate that 8.5% of EU citizens cannot afford a quality meal every second day⁶. Reducing food loss and waste therefore directly supports food security and social equity, by increasing redistribution potential and reducing pressure on household budgets.

Systemic lock-ins and barriers towards effective FLW reduction

The EU policy sets the direction towards FLW prevention and reduction, but multiple lock-ins (or roadblocks) hinder delivery. For example, the Waste Framework Directive embeds the food-waste hierarchy and obliges Member States to measure and prevent food waste, promote surplus redistribution, and report using harmonised methods. Yet, historic gaps included fragmented definitions, limited operator-level measurement, and uneven surplus-management rules, have weakened prevention incentives.

Figure 2 Lock-in effects contributing to food loss and waste

Those lock-in effects arise from multiple dimensions, including: technical bottlenecks, organisational routines, market incentives, regulatory gaps, and those related to behaviours. They are the roadblocks to the effective implementation of EU regulatory framework related to the reduction of FLW. To overcome those, a systemic approach is needed to orchestrate coordinated changes across technologies,

organisational practices, business models, governance arrangements and user behaviours, ensuring that innovations can evolve to higher levels of systemic readiness, align with regulatory requirements, and function in combination rather than in isolation. This approach which has been implemented in the ZeroW project, links actors across the supply chain, supports data availability and interoperability, reduces cooperation costs, and helps create the enabling conditions required for large-scale FLW prevention, reduction and valorisation.

⁶ Eurostat news, 28 August 2025

1.2 ZeroW – Systemic Innovation Towards Zero Waste Food Supply Chain

ZeroW is an EC-funded project under the call “H2020-LC-GD-2020: Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: Research and innovation in support of the European Green Deal”. The project focuses on significantly reducing Food Loss and Waste (FLW), aiming to halve it by 2030 and achieve near-zero levels by 2050. This goal is pursued through the development and implementation of innovations within nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) covering all stages of the food value chain: pre-harvest, post-harvest, processing and packaging, logistics and retail, and consumption.

The key areas of innovation span the full food supply chain. They include FLW monitoring and assessment through interoperable data infrastructures, pre-harvest and greenhouse optimisation aligned with short-term demand, data-driven production process control and optimisation, and machine-vision tools for early quality and shelf-life assessment. They also cover mobile on-site valorisation services, circular valorisation of retail side streams such as algae-based bioprocessing, efficiency improvements in food bank operations, consumer-facing tools for awareness and behavioural change, and innovative sustainable packaging solutions.

The project also encompasses activities to ensure the long-term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW solutions.

Figure 3 ZeroW at a glance

1.2.1 Systemic approach to change

The ZeroW approach to reducing Food Loss and Waste through systemic innovations began with pre-identifying innovations that integrate various interlinked dimensions such as process, organisational strategy, marketing, product, technological, and governance, which are then tested and demonstrated.

The next step involved steering these innovations towards higher levels of systemic readiness and impact by employing a Living Lab co-creation and multi-actor collective learning approach. This was supported by enhancing the innovation

capabilities of Living Lab participants through shared resources that facilitated new cooperation and development methods.

Finally, context-specific trajectories were developed for these innovations, guiding them from ideation to scaling up and commercialisation. This led to the creation of new products and services that meet consumer needs, align with food industry demands, and adhere to policy trends.

Figure 4 ZeroW approach

Additionally, ZeroW established a clear FLW impact trajectory, evidencing how the results can be scaled up from demonstrator results in 2025 to achieve the 2030 goals, and navigating through a just transition pathway towards near-zero FLW by 2050. The project has demonstrated how this could be achieved through the 'Policies for just transition and economic modelling' workstreams.

From a delivery perspective, ZeroW work was divided into 11 Work Packages (WPs) with distinct goals, tasks, and deliverables to achieve its objectives. The structure and organisation of work through those WPs reflect closely the systemic approach highlighted above. The 8 technical WPs included:

- Setting up, prototyping, testing, and demonstrating systemic innovation solutions for FLW reduction, along with their IT enabling environment and integration through governance models and a common dataspace (WPs 2, 3, and 4).

- Assessing impacts and providing socio-economic and environmental sustainability and scalability of the solutions, supporting their commercial advancement (WPs 5, 6, and 7).
- Defining a just transition pathway towards near-zero FLW, including setting intermediate EU targets and delivering short- and medium-term FLW policy recommendations (WPs 1 and 8).

The remaining 3 work packages offered horizontal support services to the entire project. WPs 9 and 10 focused on liaising with other relevant FLW initiatives and organisations to promote communication, collaboration, and dissemination of project results. Finally, WP 11 handled project management to ensure the successful delivery of quality results, efficient internal communication and collaboration between WPs and delivery partners, effective risk mitigation, and the identification and pursuit of opportunities. Additionally, WP 11 oversaw open and transparent data management and ethical project delivery.

Figure 5 WP11 in the overall project structure. Tasks and deliverables

The WPs interacted closely with each other to form a closed systemic feedback, connecting innovation generation, demonstration, assessment, and exploitation. The project architecture enabled bidirectional learning between demonstration and policy modelling, ensuring that project results inform medium- and long-term systemic change pathways.

1.2.2 SILLs as systemic demonstrative environments

The SILLs functioned as a multi-actor co-creation ecosystem, structured around five components: approach, learning, shared resources and infrastructure, members,

and management. This was envisaged to ensure that no single technological or organisational innovation acted in isolation but instead contributed to a coherent systemic transition. For that reason, each ZeroW living lab addressed specific system lock-ins and applied data-driven solutions to ensure future sustainability and scale-up of the innovations developed, in a just transition environment.

Table 2 Food loss and waste lock in effects and ZeroW technical innovations addressing them

Dimension	Lock-in effects	ZeroW response
Technical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited real-time visibility (yields, quality, shelf-life) leads to over-production and late detection of spoilage. • Rigid processing capacity cannot absorb variable, seasonal surpluses close to source. • Optimal harvest windows not synchronised with downstream capacity and short-term demand. • Packaging seen as secondary waste, not an FLW-reducing lever. 	SILL1 FLW monitoring and data services; SILL3 digital yield and quality prediction; SILL4 flexible/near-source valorisation capacity; SILL2 smart and compostable packaging, shelf-life signalling.
Organisational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fixed planning horizons and siloed operations hinder rapid reallocation of surplus to higher-value uses. • Limited FLW capabilities for diverse, seasonal or disruption-driven surpluses. • Limited food-bank capabilities to address supply-demand mismatches and uncertainty. 	SILL3 adaptive harvest and sourcing with buyer integration. SILL4 service model embedded in partner workflows. SILL7 coordination with food banks and last-mile logistics.
Market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Missing economic feasibility for food-grade valorisation; cost and risk favour disposal or low-value uses. • High transport costs for small, dispersed surpluses. • Value not shared fairly along the chain, dampening upstream prevention. • 'Ugly food' identification at a late stage, reduces the possibilities for alternative valorisation 	LCC/CBA and just-allocation metrics; business cases per SILL. SILL4 near-source processing to cut logistics costs. SILL5 early identification of "ugly" fruit enabling valorisation, instead of waste.
Regulatory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historic gaps in measurement and reporting; inconsistent surplus-management practices. • Marketing standards and date-mark interpretation drive avoidable waste. 	SILL1 harmonised measurement aligned with EU monitoring. WP8 policy pathways and recommendations. SILL2 clearer shelf-life cues to support date-label use.
Behavioural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inability to steer consumer buying at point of purchase; "full-shelf" norms. 	SILL2 smart labelling and nudges at retail. SILL7

Dimension	Lock-in effects	ZeroW response
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Household planning, storage and label interpretation issues. 	awareness through redistribution networks. SILL9 diet and behaviour tools for households.

The ZeroW systemic innovations can contribute to the reduction of FLW by pairing technical fixes with organisational change, fair incentives, harmonised measurement, and behaviour shifts. Most importantly, any regulatory and systemic conditions gaps impacting the successful implementation of the innovations were identified and investigated to produce meaningful policy briefs to contribute towards the objectives of the Green Deal, Farm-to-Fork, and Waste Framework Directive.

1.2.3 Systemic Innovation Readiness Level (SIRL) and learning loops

The SIRL tool, developed under WP4 (D4.1), is a central mechanism for monitoring progress and steering systemic maturity. It extends the traditional TRL concept by assessing readiness across technological, business, policy, behavioural, and value-chain dimensions, using participatory workshops within each SILL.

SIRL assessments were conducted iteratively through three measurement rounds (R1–R3), capturing the evolution of each SILL’s systemic readiness and providing feedback to improve innovation design and stakeholder cooperation. The resulting data were integrated to inform scaling strategies and for monitoring overall systemic progress of the project.

ZeroW not only developed systemic solutions to reduce food loss and waste but also organised its own work in a systemic and structured way. The project applied the SIRL methodology to guide and monitor progress across all SILLs, creating continuous feedback loops between the Living Labs and the thematic Work Packages. This framework ensured that data, lessons, and insights were shared in real time across technical, organisational, assessment, exploitation and scaling, policy and dissemination work streams. The strong collaboration among consortium partners and continuous engagement with external stakeholders maintained the project’s multi-actor and multidisciplinary nature. The systematic delivery process in ZeroW allowed the project to make evidence-based decisions and to formulate policy recommendations grounded in high-quality data, ensuring that the proposed solutions support effective and equitable governance of food-loss-and-waste reduction across both local and European levels.

1.3 Addressing the GA requirements

The purpose of this chapter is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, from the formal Deliverable and Task descriptions to the chapters of this document. This Deliverable originates from WP11, Project Management, Task 11.4 – ZeroW overall impact assessment. The task performs an overall assessment of ZeroW outputs by using the targeted SILL impacts defined in the project’s Grant Agreement.

Table 3 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE: D11.4 ZeroW impact assessment - Will present an overall assessment of the project impact.		
TASK: T11.4 ZeroW overall impact assessment		
T11.4 ZeroW overall impact assessment (Lead: ICP) (M44-M48): In this Task, an overall assessment of ZeroW outputs will be performed, by employing a broad participatory approach involving external stakeholders as assessors of the extent to which the project has achieved its foreseen impacts, i.e.:	Entire document	This document consolidates the overall impact assessment of ZeroW by evaluating all project impacts against the Grant Agreement requirements and incorporating evidence from SILL demonstrations, cross-WP analyses and stakeholder validation to determine the extent to which the project has achieved its foreseen outcomes. A broad participatory approach, involving both SILL participants and relevant non-beneficiary stakeholders, helped to shape and verify the results.
(i) to demonstrate innovative systemic solutions that have the potential to generate significant positive impacts by 2030 with regards to:		
(a) reducing food losses and waste and the use of unsustainable packaging, at every stage of the food chain including consumption,	Section 2.1 and 2.3	Sections 2.1 and 2.3 demonstrate how the systemic solutions piloted in the nine SILLs have delivered measurable reductions in food losses and waste and decreases in unsustainable packaging across all stages of the food chain
(b) providing sufficient, safe, nutritious, healthy and affordable food for all,	Section 2.4	Section 2.4 shows how the innovations contribute to providing sufficient, safe, nutritious, healthy and affordable food by improving food availability, supporting safer production and handling practices, and strengthening access to nutritious products through more efficient and less wasteful supply chains.

ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
(c) improving the overall sustainability of food systems,	Section 2.5	Section 2.5 summarises how the demonstrated innovations enhance the overall sustainability of food systems by reducing environmental pressures, strengthening economic viability across actors and supporting socially equitable outcomes.
(d) improving the resilience of food systems to shocks and stresses;	Section 2.6	Section 2.6 explains how the demonstrated innovations strengthen the resilience of food systems by improving adaptive capacity, reducing vulnerability to disruptions and supporting more robust operational and supply chain practices.
(ii) to contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the Farm-to-Fork Strategy and The European Green Deal, and in particular to:		
(a) halving the per capita food waste at retail and consumer levels by 2030,	Section 2.1	Section 2.1 outlines how the demonstrated reductions in food waste across retail and consumer settings contribute directly to the Farm-to-Fork and European Green Deal objective of halving per capita food waste by 2030.
(b) reducing GHG-emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared with 1990 levels;	Section 2.2	Section 2.2 shows how the achieved and projected GHG reductions from the demonstrated FLW prevention, reduction and valorisation solutions contribute to the Farm-to-Fork and European Green Deal objective.
(iii) to achieve an increase in awareness among policy makers, businesses, investors, entrepreneurs, institutions, stakeholders and citizens of selected innovative systemic solutions, of their potential and of the requirements to promote and realise their uptake at EU scale and behavioural change.	Section 2.7	Section 2.7 demonstrates how the project broad engagement and dissemination activities increased awareness among policymakers, businesses, investors, entrepreneurs, institutions, stakeholders and citizens of the systemic solutions, their potential and the conditions needed for their uptake and behavioural change at EU scale.
The targeted SILL impacts defined in section 2.1, will be used (among others) for assessing the overall impact of the project.	Section 2	Section 2 as a whole applies the targeted SILL impacts as defined in the Grant Agreement as the core reference points for assessing the project's overall impact, drawing on quantified results and evidence from all SILL demonstrations.

1.4 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable is organised to provide a clear and traceable account of how the ZeroW project impacts and achievements have been assessed based on empirical data.

- **Chapter 1** introduces the context of food loss and waste in the EU and outlines the ZeroW project's systemic approach, including the role of the SILLs, the Systemic Innovation Readiness Level (SIRL) framework and the wider project architecture. It also maps the GA requirements to the contents of this deliverable and provides an overview of the assessment methodology, including the impact-assessment framework, data sources and analytical links with other work packages.
- **Chapter 2** presents the assessment of the achieved impacts. It is structured directly around the impact categories defined in the Grant Agreement and provides the final, validated results for each one. The chapter draws on data from the SILLs and from the analytical work carried out in WPs 1, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10. Each subsection explains how the demonstrated innovations contributed to a specific impact and reports the final quantitative outcomes using the indicators and methods defined in D5.1, D5.2 and D5.3. The chapter also details the SILL-specific performance at each food supply chain stage, ensuring that the assessment is fully anchored in empirical project evidence.
- **Chapter 3** focuses on the post-project impacts. It summarises the expected medium- and long-term reductions in FLW and GHG emissions, based on the modelling carried out in WP1 and the transition pathways and policy analysis developed in WP8. The chapter explains how the demonstrated innovations, when scaled and supported by appropriate policy measures, contribute to achieving the 2030 and 2050 targets of the Farm to Fork Strategy and the European Green Deal.
- **Chapter 4** presents the key challenges, barriers and gaps identified across the project. It brings together findings from the SILL demonstrations, as well as from the business, policy and scaling work carried out in WPs 6, 7 and 8, and from stakeholder engagement activities.
- **Chapter 5** offers the conclusions and recommendations. It synthesises the overall achievements of ZeroW relative to the Grant Agreement targets, reflects on the relevance of the systemic innovation approach and summarises the broader contribution of the project to EU food-system objectives. The chapter provides final remarks on the implications for policy, scaling and long-term impact potential.

These chapters provide a structured and comprehensive account of the project impact assessment and show how the evidence supports ZeroW’s contribution to a sustainable, resilient and near-zero FLW food system.

1.5 Methodological overview

1.5.1 Impact assessment framework

The overall project impact assessment applied in this document, builds directly on several key deliverables related to impact assessment, each with its own focus, methodological depth, and scope of analysis. These deliverables have formed a coherent sequence that has enabled the project to measure, interpret, and report its impacts at different levels of maturity - from individual SILLs to the overall project scale.

Figure 6 ZeroW impact assessment framework

D5.1 – Impact Assessment Methodology, established the methodological foundation for assessing the environmental, economic, social, and FSC-actors related impacts of the project’s innovations. It defined the combined use of the Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) framework, integrating Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Social LCA (S-LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC), alongside Cost–Benefit Analysis (CBA) and the Systemic Innovation Readiness Level (SIRL) approach. D5.1 ensured consistency and comparability across all Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) by providing common templates, indicators, and evaluation criteria to guide the subsequent impact assessments.

The data and core indicators were then compiled in D5.2 - SILLs Impacts Assessment. Building on the framework defined in D5.1, this task and its resulting report assessed the multiple rounds of measurements for the SILLs, thus forming the quantitative “backbone” for ZeroW impact evidence.

The analysis further extended beyond individual SILLs to interpret the results at the project level through several analytical perspectives documented in D5.3 – Results interpretation. The goal of D5.3 was to contextualise the results and identify cross-cutting insights by analysing how innovation performance differs under various environmental, geographical, and social conditions and how they impact the different FSC actors/clusters.

The purpose of the current deliverable is to serve as the final project-level assessment, examining how ZeroW demonstrated innovations and actions align with the impact targets defined in the Grant Agreement.

It synthesises and consolidates the findings from D5.1–D5.3 to evaluate how the project has delivered on its expected impacts. D11.4 represents, in this sense, the final analytical step in the project’s impact-assessment pathway, translating the detailed SILL-level and contextual analyses into a single and verifiable narrative of ZeroW contribution to the EU Green Deal and Farm to Fork strategy objectives.

The logical progression and interconnections between these deliverables are illustrated in *Figure 6* above, showing how common input data - namely SILLs’ impact achievement KPIs and related parameters defined in the GA - feed through each analytical stage to reach the overall impact evaluation presented here.

1.5.2 Data sources and links with other WPs

The overall impact assessment presented in this deliverable integrates data and analytical inputs originating from several work packages of ZeroW. Each WP contributes complementary evidence to ensure that the assessment captures environmental, economic, social, and FSC actors’/clusters dimensions of impact across the project.

Figure 7 Links and data inputs from the rest of the ZeroW work packages

- WP1 and WP8 – Modelling of Food Loss and Waste (FLW) scenarios and defining transition pathways

These work packages provide model-based evidence supporting the medium- and long-term assessment of food-loss-and-waste reduction. WP8 defines the scenario framework and long-term transition pathways, while WP1 applies empirical economic and behavioural modelling within those scenarios. They provide evidence on the economic and behavioural mechanisms influencing FLW generation under different policy and market conditions. Their combined outputs inform D11.4 by identifying how interventions and incentive structures can support progress toward the Farm-to-Fork objective of halving FLW by 2030, and by outlining the economic preconditions for a just transition toward near-zero FLW by 2050.

- WP2, WP3 and WP4 – Generation and facilitation of empirical data from demonstrators

Data generated/managed within these WPs supply the empirical evidence underpinning the SILL operations and assessments. They include operational data, primary measurements, stakeholder feedback, and contextual parameters that describe how innovations perform in real operating environments.

- WP5 – Impacts data collection and analysis

Under WP5, the data gathered from demonstrators were systematically processed and analysed through the integrated framework defined in D5.1 (Impact Assessment Methodology). The inputs from WP2/3/4 were consolidated in D5.2 - SILLs Impacts Assessment, which produced the baseline, first, second and third round of quantitative results on FLW reduction, GHG emissions, sustainability trade-offs, and just-transition outcomes. As described in the previous subsection, D5.2 and D5.3 reflect the quantitative and interpretative outputs of this work.

- WP6 – Scaling and replication

WP6 supplied information on achieved scalability and replication potential of SILL solutions. These data complement the SIRL (Systemic Innovation Readiness Level) results from WP4&5 by illustrating how local demonstrations could expand to regional or EU-wide applications.

- WP7 – Innovation exploitation and commercialisation

This WP provided evidence on the commercial and innovation-readiness dimensions of the project, including the number of patents filed, partners' commercial intentions and business models. Those inputs are used in D11.4 to characterise the economic viability impacts of the demonstrated innovations.

- WP9 and WP10 – Awareness, dissemination, and behavioural change

Outputs from these WPs contribute qualitative data on awareness raising, communication reach, stakeholder engagement, and behavioural change

indicators. They underpin the interpretation of Impact 7 (Increased Awareness and Behavioural Change) presented further down in the document in Section 2.7.

All these data streams converge in D11.4, where they are synthesised to evaluate ZeroW overall performance against the impact targets defined in the Grant Agreement. No new primary data collection has been undertaken for this deliverable: all quantitative and qualitative evidence is derived from validated project outputs, approved deliverables, and partner datasets stored in the project repository.

1.5.3 Impact categories

The ZeroW project aimed to contribute significantly to the objectives and targets set by the Farm-to-Fork Strategy and the European Green Deal through its nine Systemic Innovations Living Labs. By 2025, these living labs were expected to achieve a 24.8% reduction in average food loss and waste and a 24.5% reduction specifically at the retail and consumer levels. Additionally, the project anticipated a 15% decrease in the use of unsustainable packaging and an 18% increase in shelf-life due to smart packaging solutions.

Figure 8 Key ZeroW Expected Impacts

Additionally, the project anticipated a 15% decrease in the use of unsustainable packaging and an 18% increase in shelf-life due to smart packaging solutions.

These environmental benefits are significant, with a projected 22.7% reduction in FLW-induced greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, food availability at food banks was expected to rise by 20%.

The project aimed to file three patents, influence two key actions of the EU Farm to Fork Strategy, and upscale three macro-regional strategies. A hundred organisations

have benefited directly from the project's innovations, which have seen their technology readiness levels increase from 5 to 7/8.

The project's reach is extensive, impacting 700,000 consumers and engaging 1 million food actors and consumers across 70 EU regions. Detailed descriptions of these impacts are provided in the following subsections.

The ZeroW project's objectives and impacts are intricately linked, ensuring a comprehensive approach to reducing food loss and waste (FLW) while promoting sustainability (Figure 9). The primary objective was to set up and test systemic innovation solutions (Objective 1), which directly supports the expected reduction in food loss and waste (Impact 1 and Impact 3). These innovations were designed to contribute significantly to the goals of the Farm-to-Fork Strategy and the European Green Deal, by halving per capita food waste at retail and consumer levels by 2030 and reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 50% by 2050 (Impact 1 and Impact 2). This framework will reinforce the expected impacts on reducing food waste and unsustainable packaging at every stage of the supply chain (Impact 3).

To support these solutions, the project aimed to establish a data-driven FLW intelligence service and ensure interoperability through a European OFLW Data Space (Objectives 2 and 3).

Assessing the impacts, risks, and sustainability trade-offs of these innovations (Objective 4) is important for understanding their broader implications, directly feeding into improving the overall sustainability of food systems (Impact 5).

Moreover, the project sought to scale up these solutions (Objective 5) and advance them commercially (Objective 6), engage with policy makers and create awareness among key stakeholders (Objective 8), which is pivotal for achieving behavioural changes and ensuring the uptake of these innovations at the EU scale (Impact 7). Additionally, defining a just transition pathway to near-zero FLW (Objective 7) aligns with delivering medium- and long-term policy recommendations, further enhancing the abovementioned expected Impact 7.

These objectives and impacts create a cohesive framework that not only targets immediate reductions in food loss and waste but also aims to transform the food system to be more sustainable, resilient, and equitable.

The project is set to achieve seven significant impacts in alignment with the LC-GD-6-1-2020 topic "Testing and demonstrating systemic innovations in support of the Farm-to-Fork Strategy". The key elements of those are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9. The following sections describe and evaluate the impacts planned in the project's GA, their evolution from inception to project completion and achieved final results:

Figure 9 Links between ZeroW project's objectives and expected impacts

- **Impact 1:** Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to halving the per capita food waste at retail and consumer levels by 2030
- **Impact 2:** Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to reducing GHG-emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared with 1990 levels.
- **Impact 3:** Reduce food losses and waste and the use of unsustainable packaging, at every stage of the food chain including consumption
- **Impact 4:** Provide sufficient, safe, nutritious, healthy and affordable food for all.
- **Impact 5:** Improve the overall sustainability of food systems (social/health, climate/environmental and economic).
- **Impact 6:** Improve the resilience of food systems to shocks and stresses.
- **Impact 7:** Achieve an increase in awareness among policy makers, businesses, investors, entrepreneurs, institutions, stakeholders and citizens of selected innovative systemic solutions, of their potential and of the requirements to promote and realise their uptake at EU scale and behavioural change

In the Grant Agreement, Impacts 1 and 3 both include targets for the reduction of food loss and waste (FLW), but they cover different stages of the food supply chain. Impact 1 focuses on the reduction of per-capita food waste at the retail and consumer levels, while Impact 3 addresses post-harvest and processing stages, and additionally includes the reduction of unsustainable packaging. For methodological clarity and to avoid duplication, D11.4 combines the FLW-related elements of Impacts 1 and 3 into a single analytical category, entitled “Reduction of Food Loss and Waste Across the Food Supply Chain.” This unified section presents results across all FSC stages: post-harvest, processing, retail, and consumption, offering a comprehensive picture of ZeroW contribution to FLW reduction.

The packaging component of Impact 3, which involves distinct indicators and targets related to material substitution and circularity, is analysed separately in Section 2.3.

1.5.4 Limitations, assumptions, and data boundaries

The limitations, assumptions, and data boundaries applied in this deliverable are inherited from the methodological framework established in D5.1 and the subsequent assessments in D5.2 and D5.3. For transparency and detailed reference, refer to those deliverables, which document the scope definitions, boundary conditions, and methodological constraints used throughout the ZeroW impact assessment process.

2. ZeroW impacts achievement

The following subsections evaluate ZeroW performance against each expected impact. Each section outlines how the individual SILL innovations contribute to the specific impact, illustrated through practical examples. The evaluation highlights the systemic lock-in effects addressed in relation to the impact and concludes with the demonstrators' achieved results, drawing on quantitative evidence from D5.2-SILL impact assessment and interpretative findings from D5.3-Results interpretation.

2.1 Reduction of Food Loss and Waste Across the Food Supply Chain (in Impacts 1 and 3)

As its name implies, the ZeroW project targeted the reduction of food loss and waste across the entire food supply chain, addressing every stage from farm to fork. Through the innovations demonstrated in the Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs), the project aimed to achieve measurable reductions in food loss and waste at the post-harvest, processing, retail and distribution, and consumption stages, as evidenced at the project completion.

Across all food-supply-chain stages, the project outperformed the expected short-term targets set in the Grant Agreement. The results confirm that the combined systemic and data-driven approach implemented through the SILLs has effectively delivered, and in most cases significantly exceeded, the project planned short-term impacts across the entire food chain. This section outlines how these reductions were realised.

Post-harvest

At the post-harvest stage, three SILLs (**SILL3**, **SILL4** and **SILL5**) developed and validated complementary solutions that address different causes of food loss and waste in early food-supply-chain operations. They target inefficiencies in forecasting, quality management, logistics, and valorisation that typically occur between harvesting and initial processing.

SILL3 focused on reducing post-harvest losses through precision monitoring and adaptive harvest management. By integrating real-time sensing, computer vision, AI-based forecasting, and digital decision-support tools, this innovation enables producers to predict yield quantity and quality with greater accuracy and to plan harvesting schedules in line with market demand and downstream

Figure 10 Wasteless greenhouse solutions (SILL3)

processing capacity. This prevents premature or delayed harvesting, which often leads to downgrading or disposal. It also supports the early identification of produce that does not meet primary-market specifications, allowing farmers to decide whether to remove it early in the growth cycle or direct it to alternative valorisation pathways.

Figure 11 Real time sensing and computer vision integration in SILL3

In doing so, **SILL3** addressed key technological and organisational lock-in effects leading to food loss and waste, namely the lack of real-time quality data, limited coordination between producers and buyers, and routine harvesting practices based on fixed calendars rather than actual field conditions.

SILL4 tackled post-harvest waste by implementing flexible, near-source valorisation of surplus and side streams. Many agricultural by-products and class B produce are lost due to high transport costs, perishability, or a lack of accessible processing options, or because harvesting and logistics costs exceed potential revenue. The SILL demonstrated local and modular processing units that can operate close

Figure 12 Flexible food valorisation as a service (SILL4)

to farms or collection points, converting perishable surpluses into food-grade ingredients or other valuable outputs before spoilage occurs. This decentralised approach reduces the need for long-distance transport, improves resource-recovery efficiency, and keeps biomass within the food chain for longer, directly lowering waste volumes.

By introducing flexible infrastructure and local cooperation models, **SILL4** overcomes infrastructural and economic lock-ins such as the rigidity of centralised processing systems, high transport costs, and the limited profitability of small-scale surplus valorisation.

SILL5 contributed to post-harvest FLW reduction through the early identification and valorisation of non-standard or “imperfect” produce. The SILL introduced intelligent mechanisms for sorting and redirecting products that fall outside retail appearance or organic-produce standards but remain safe and nutritious. It prevents waste arising from post-delivery rejection by retailers, whether due to cosmetic imperfections, minor spoilage, or deviation from strict organic requirements, and also avoids the FLW associated transport and logistical inefficiencies.

Figure 13 “Ugly” food identification at post-harvest level (SILL5)

SILL5 specifically addressed market and behavioural lock-ins linked to rigid aesthetic standards, risk-averse procurement practices, and the lack of traceability once goods leave the producer, transforming produce previously rejected as waste into valuable inputs for further processing or redistribution.

The three SILLs illustrate a coherent systemic strategy for post-harvest FLW reduction: **SILL3** prevented losses before they occur, **SILL4** established efficient valorisation routes for unavoidable surpluses, and **SILL5** ensured that quality standards and procurement practices no longer act as barriers to food use.

The implementation of these three SILLs has led by the end of the project to substantial reductions in food loss and waste at the post-harvest stage, significantly exceeding the levels initially planned in the Grant Agreement.

Impact type	FSC stage	GA planned	Participating SILLs	Achieved FLW reduction
FLW reduction	Post-harvest	-24.8%	SILL3	-36%
			SILL4	-84%
			SILL5	-100%
	Achieved average FLW reduction			-73%

Against the target of a 25% reduction, the achieved results demonstrate the combined effectiveness of the systemic approach:

- **SILL3** achieved an estimated 36% reduction in post-harvest losses through precision monitoring and adaptive harvest management;
- **SILL4** reached an 84% reduction by enabling near-source valorisation of surplus and side streams; and

- **SILL5** recorded a 100% reduction through early identification and valorisation of non-standard produce.

Overall, this corresponds to an average post-harvest reduction of approximately 73%, evidencing the strong potential of data-driven, locally embedded and cross-actor innovations to prevent losses at the earliest stages of the food supply chain.

Processing

At the food processing stage, **SILL4** and **SILL6** developed complementary innovations targeting inefficiencies that lead to waste generation during the transformation of raw materials into finished food products. Both SILLs addressed different but interconnected sources of food loss and waste (FLW), focusing respectively on valorisation of side streams and optimisation of process control.

Figure 14 Flexible, small scale processing (Sill4)

SILL4 extended its post-harvest activities into the processing stage by implementing a flexible, service-oriented model for mobile and local food valorisation. The SILL addressed the large variability of food surpluses and underutilised edible biomass fractions in regions with intensive fruit and vegetable production, where small producers and social organisations often lack the capacity

or infrastructure to process these surpluses into higher-value food products.

The solution combines mobile processing units and regional valorisation hubs equipped with adaptable small-scale technologies such as GEA Vaculiq vacuum juicing, MultiCut systems, and pasteurisation lines. These allow quick transformation of second-class or market-removed fruit and vegetables into juices, smoothies, and soups, extending shelf life and keeping edible biomass in the food chain. In the project's final year, the SILL demonstrated this concept at several sites in Belgium, including the Food Bank Limburg (VBL) and Fructus Juice in Borgloon, where tomato soup and fruit juices produced from second-class tomatoes and mixed fruits were redistributed to people in need via local food banks.

SILL4 also developed a progressive web-based decision-support tool that matches available feedstock with optimal processing options and recipes, enabling small actors to plan production efficiently based on real-time surpluses. The model's business logic - "valorisation as a service", allows farmers, cooperatives, and small

enterprises to process surplus produce without major investments in equipment by using the hub's shared facilities.

Figure 15 Valorisation of class B and side streams (SILL4)

SILL4 directly addressed several systemic lock-in effects identified in the Grant Agreement. It mitigates technological and infrastructural lock-ins by providing accessible, small-scale processing capacity close to production sites, reducing dependence on centralised systems and long-distance logistics. It addressed economic lock-ins by lowering the costs and risks associated with small-volume valorisation, making it financially

viable for local actors to recover value from edible surpluses. In parallel, it responded to organisational and behavioural lock-ins by promoting cooperation and shared responsibility across farmers, processors, food banks, and local authorities - actors that traditionally operate in isolation.

Figure 16 Data driven production process control (SILL6) - Use case 1 and 2

SILL6 on the other hand focused on reducing food waste at the processing stage through the application of smart process optimisation and predictive quality control in the poultry sector. Food losses during meat processing often result from over-processing, suboptimal temperature management, and the rejection of products that deviate from quality specifications. To address these challenges, **SILL6** developed and demonstrated data-driven, sensor-based monitoring systems that integrate real-time process data into decision-making, helping operators maintain consistent product quality and minimise avoidable waste and increase the percentage of food that passes quality control.

Figure 17 Data driven production process control (SILL6) – Use case 3

The SILL carried out three main use cases within industrial poultry-processing environments. In the first two, a near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy system was implemented to monitor chicken and poultry mince during production. This enabled the detection of deviations in key quality parameters such as salt and moisture content, composition, and freshness in real time, reducing the risk of unnecessary batch rejections caused by uncertainty about product quality. The third use case focused on optimising the defrosting process of frozen chicken meat. By integrating temperature and time sensors with predictive algorithms, the process was adjusted to achieve optimal defrosting conditions, preserving texture and safety while avoiding product losses due to overexposure or partial spoilage. The use cases successfully demonstrated how digital process control can extend shelf life, improve yield, and substantially reduce waste generated during processing.

SILL6 addressed several systemic lock-in effects that contribute to waste in the food processing sector. It mitigated technological lock-ins associated with limited process transparency, insufficient use of real-time quality data, and the absence of predictive control mechanisms. At the same time, it tackled organisational lock-ins stemming from rigid production routines, limited integration between production and quality-control systems. Finally, by increasing operators' confidence in data-supported decisions, the solution also helped overcome behavioural lock-ins linked to risk aversion and the perception that product safety requires conservative rejection margins.

The two SILLs demonstrated a complementary and systemic strategy for reducing food loss and waste at the processing stage: **SILL4** focused on the valorisation of side streams and underused edible biomass through local processing and service-based models, while **SILL6** prevented waste generation by improving process control and predictive quality management in poultry processing.

Impact type	FSC stage	GA planned	Participating SILLs	Achieved FLW reduction
FLW reduction	Food processing	-25.0%	SILL4	-67%
			SILL6	-44%
	Achieved average FLW reduction			-55%

By the end of the project, the implementation of these two SILLs resulted in substantial reductions in food loss and waste at the processing stage, well above the levels initially planned in the Grant Agreement. Against a target reduction of 25%, **SILL4** achieved a 67% decrease in FLW through flexible, near-source valorisation, and **SILL6** achieved a 44% reduction by preventing losses in meat-processing operations. On average, this corresponds to a 55% reduction in food loss and waste across the processing stage, confirming that ZeroW integrated approach, combining technological innovation, digitalisation, and new business models, has effectively delivered transformative results within a core segment of the food supply chain.

Retail

At the retail stage, four SILLs (**SILL2**, **SILL5**, **SILL7** and **SILL8**) demonstrated complementary innovations that reduce food waste arising from short remaining shelf life, rigid in-store practices, fragmented donation flows, and the absence of viable valorisation pathways for unavoidable surplus.

Figure 18 Innovative, sustainable and smart packaging (SILL2)

SILL2 targeted waste from fresh fish by combining compostable barrier materials, a compartmentalised tray that keeps exudates away from the product, and an intelligent freshness indicator readable via a mobile app. The packaging developed with ITENE and validated in Eroski's retail environment and through consumer focus group extends shelf life and provides dynamic freshness

information. Retailers can rotate, discount, or redistribute products based on actual condition rather than static expiry dates. This dual effect (slower spoilage and more accurate freshness visibility) directly reduces product discards. The innovation addresses technological lock-ins such as the lack of real-time freshness data, as well as behavioural ones linked to conservative date-based stock rotation.

Generally, biobased materials used for food packaging do not perform as well as traditional fossil-based plastics. Their higher permeability to oxygen and humidity tends to accelerate spoilage and shorten shelf life. Biobased packaging with shelf life performance comparable to fossil-based materials is not yet commercially available, which is why such options are rarely used for high-value and highly perishable products such as oily fish.

The advances achieved in **SILL2** therefore represent one of the first meaningful breakthroughs in this area. The team developed a fully biobased and compostable packaging solution that overcomes the typical permeability limitations and delivers shelf life results that meet, and in some cases exceed, those of conventional fossil-based packaging.

Two elements drove this improvement. First, the barrier coating applied to the thin lid film reduced the oxygen transmission rate from about 800 units (uncoated film) to between 2 and 5 units, bringing its performance close to that of fossil-based films. Second, the introduction of a permeable membrane created a controlled separation between the exudate and the fish, avoiding the direct contact that typically occurs with absorbent pads in conventional packaging. This contributed further to maintaining product quality.

Figure 19 For accurate reading, the colour change can be read by a mobile app

The initial tests demonstrated that the food preservation properties of the biobased packaging are comparable with the traditional packaging. If the comparison were made against other biobased packaging materials, the gains would be even more pronounced. A full assessment was not possible within the project, as comparable biobased packaging solutions (trays) are not yet available for products of this type. The smart label provides retailers and consumers with additional information that supports better handling and consumption decisions. It indicates the actual freshness of the product and shows that it can be safely consumed for an average

of 1.4 days beyond the printed use by date (normally 9 days for Eroski products and 7 days for the other retailers). The reduction in food waste is calculated on the basis of this extended, freshness-verified shelf life.

SILL5 contributed to retail-stage FLW reduction through objective quality verification and shelf-life prediction of fresh produce, particularly cherry tomatoes, using NG Sensors' spectrometry and Multiscan's multispectral imaging systems. These technologies, deployed with FCTA, IFAPA, Grupo La Caña and Multiscan, allow automatic measurement of freshness, composition, and organic compliance for each batch before it enters the store. In practice, this enables retailers to validate product quality at goods reception, avoiding the premature rejection or downgrading of entire lots based on uncertain visual inspection.

Figure 20 Objective quality identification at retail level (SILL5)

The sensor data also supports in-store stock management: lots nearing the verified end of shelf life can be prioritised for quick sale or redistribution, while batches that do not meet premium standards can be reclassified for alternative markets rather than wasted. The tests reported in D5.2 show that 10–20% of tomatoes previously discarded due to mislabelling, visual deviations or shelf-life uncertainty were successfully redirected, and losses from destructive testing were almost fully eliminated. By giving retailers confidence in measured rather than estimated product quality, **SILL5** tackled systemic lock-ins such as the absence of shelf-life visibility, rigid quality acceptance policies, and the lack of communication between producers and retail quality control.

SILL7 focused on reducing waste through better management of products approaching their use-by dates and optimising redistribution of unsold food. Working with food retailers and food banks, the SILL developed operational guidance for prioritising discounting versus donation depending on product type, safety status and remaining shelf life. For example, for products approaching their expiry date, the SILL provided guidance on when discounting or donation is more appropriate, distinguishing between short-shelf-life chilled goods (such as dairy, fresh meat, or ready meals) and longer-life or ambient products suitable for redistribution (such as packaged groceries, bakery items, or canned foods). This structured approach helps retailers act before expiry, preventing last-minute decisions that often result in disposal.

Figure 21 "De-wasting" on retail level through efficient redistribution (SILL7)

The SILL also produced a practical handbook and training materials to standardise donation workflows, clarify food-safety responsibilities, and improve coordination with redistribution partners. These measures reduced avoidable waste by aligning internal retail processes with the capacities and timing of receiving organisations. **SILL7** addressed organisational lock-ins such as fragmented internal responsibilities for markdowns and donations, lack of clear protocols for redistributing chilled goods, and limited coordination between store operations and charitable recipients.

Figure 22 Retail FW valorisation through microalgae production (SILL8)

SILL8 demonstrated a retail-level valorisation pathway for unsold food that cannot be donated, ensuring that even residual surpluses are prevented from becoming waste. The SILL established a dehydration and stabilisation process for mixed food waste directly at retail sites or distribution hubs, enabling their safe storage and later transport to microalgae production facilities, for use as feedstock in microalgae cultivation. This approach maintains some nutritional value of inedible food while avoiding microbial degradation, allowing it to re-enter the bio-based value chain instead of the waste stream. The in-store dehydration solution has been implemented across eight MC SONAE supermarkets in Portugal. It is expected that, once commercial validation is complete and the dehydrator is certified for processing animal products, together with regulatory approval for using microalgae grown on this substrate in applications such as cosmetics, biomaterials, and bio-fertilisers/bio-stimulants, the solution could be replicated across the retailer's remaining large stores.

SILL8's innovation created a practical valorisation route for non-donatable unsold food which prevents food waste generation at source and transforms unavoidable residues into valuable bio-based resources. It addressed technological lock-ins linked to the lack of cost-effective small-scale valorisation infrastructure at retail

level and economic lock-ins associated with high transport and disposal costs, demonstrating that even the final retail surplus can be retained within the circular bioeconomy.

The four SILLs’ innovations demonstrated a coherent systemic strategy for reducing food loss and waste at the retail stage. Each innovation targets a distinct but complementary point of intervention along the in-store and redistribution chain: from extending product shelf life and improving quality verification, to enabling timely discounting, donation, and valorisation of unavoidable surplus. Their combined implementation illustrated how coordinated technological and organisational changes can substantially reduce food waste across diverse retail settings.

Impact type	FSC stage	GA planned	Participating SILLs	Achieved FLW reduction
FLW reduction	Retail	-20.0%	SILL2	-4.2%
			SILL5	-20% - -10%
			SILL7	-74%
			SILL8	-54% - -40%
	Achieved average FLW reduction			-35%

Against the 20% reduction target in the Grant Agreement, the four SILLs jointly deliver an average 35% reduction at retail. **SILL2** extends shelf life and exposes true smart packaging, **SILL5** enables verified quality and targeted stock management, **SILL7** guides efficient discounting and donation decisions, and **SILL8** valorises unavoidable surplus through dehydration and bio-based reuse. Collectively these four innovations demonstrate that integrating sensor technology, operational guidance, and circular valorisation can transform the retail segment into a proactive hub of food waste prevention and resource recovery.

Consumption

At the consumption stage, two SILLs (**SILL2** and **SILL9**) demonstrated complementary innovations targeting food waste generated in households. Their actions focused on allowing the consumers to make informed decisions about product freshness, storage, and cooking deadline, while encouraging awareness of the link between food use, nutrition, and environmental impact.

Figure 23 Prototype of the smart packaging, integrating biodegradable barrier for shelf life extension and smart, colour changing indicator for the freshness status of the fish (SILL2)

SILL2 contributed to food-waste reduction at the consumption stage through the introduction of a smart packaging system with an integrated freshness indicator designed for direct interpretation by consumers. The colour-based label enables end users to easily assess the product's actual condition at home. The indicator changes colour according to the salmon's biochemical status, helping consumers distinguish between "fresh," "consume soon," and "no longer suitable" rather than relying solely on printed expiry dates. The focus group with EROSKI consumers confirmed the label's effectiveness: 90% said it would help them reduce food waste by showing when to cook or consume the product, 70% felt more confident keeping food longer instead of discarding it too early, and all participants stated the label increased their trust in product freshness. In addition, 100% said they would be more likely to purchase products with such packaging in the future. Combined with the tray's biodegradable barrier materials and exudate-separating design, which slow spoilage and extend shelf life, the packaging enables households to use food safely closer to its real end of life. **SILL2** therefore addressed informational and behavioural lock-ins that lead to unnecessary household waste: confusion over expiry dates, uncertainty about freshness, and lack of confidence in assessing food safety.

METRIC	TOTAL	PER DAY / PERSON
Total Carbon (g)	37318.30	3109.86
Total Land Use (m ²)	18.91	1.58
Waste (g)	547.00	45.58
Total Cost (€)	47.93	3.99

SILL9 addressed household food waste by supporting consumers in planning, purchasing, and cooking food more efficiently. It combined two complementary tools: the Wasteless Family Cooking Recipes & App and a Food Waste-awareness label.

The app generates weekly meal plans and shopping lists optimised to ensure that all purchased ingredients are fully used across the week, preventing leftovers and unused items. Its underlying model balances four criteria: low food waste, high nutritional value, affordability, and low environmental impact, so that consumers can plan meals that are both sustainable and practical. The app provides recipes calibrated for an average household of four people, which can be adapted to other household sizes. Each plan sequences meals strategically, using ingredients in multiple dishes and prioritising perishable foods earlier in the week to minimise spoilage.

Complementing the app, the Food Waste-awareness label presents easy-to-read indicators showing the environmental and food-waste impact of meals and ingredients. These visual cues help consumers understand the broader footprint of their choices and promote more sustainable consumption patterns. The app and label were designed using data from Dutch supermarket partners such as Ahold and Jumbo to ensure that recipes and packaging sizes reflect real market conditions.

The **SILL9** developed tools address several consumer-specific lock-ins identified in the

project: lack of structured meal planning, limited understanding of how everyday choices affect food waste, and the absence of clear feedback linking purchase, preparation, and disposal. By making planning intuitive and providing visibility into the sustainability of meals, **SILL9** enable households to act on waste-prevention goals in daily routines. Early testing indicates very strong potential for behaviour change, with ongoing trials among students and families confirming that the approach helps consumers plan more efficiently, buy only what they need, and make fuller use of purchased ingredients, therefore eliminating the food waste⁷.

SILL2 and **SILL9** demonstrated a coherent systemic strategy for food-waste reduction at the consumption stage. **SILL2** provides the objective product freshness status information that prevents premature disposal, while **SILL9** enables better meal planning and sustainable food choices. Their combined implementation illustrates how coordinated technological and informational interventions can empower households to substantially reduce food waste.

Household-level or consumer-generated food waste represents the largest share of total food waste across the food supply chain, making this stage particularly critical for achieving the overall ZeroW objectives. The results from **SILL2** and **SILL9** show that practical, user-oriented solutions, combining smart packaging, digital guidance, and sustainability information, can effectively address this challenge and translate awareness into measurable waste prevention.

Impact type	FSC stage	GA planned	Participating SILLs	Achieved FLW reduction
FLW reduction	Consumption	-25.0%	SILL2	-4.2%
			SILL9	-100%
	Achieved average FLW reduction			-52%

Against the 25% reduction target in the Grant Agreement, the two SILLs jointly achieved an average 52% decrease in food waste at the consumption stage. **SILL2** improves household decision-making on freshness and safe use of perishable products, while **SILL9** helps families plan meals efficiently and align consumption with sustainability goals. These innovations confirm that the consumption stage holds the greatest potential for impact and that empowering households through accessible, data-driven tools is essential to reaching near-zero food waste outcomes.

⁷ The test was conducted with a small sample of households for a week, demonstrating that if adhered to, the meal planning app can eliminate the household food waste completely.

2.2 Reduction of Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Emissions Related to FLW (Impact 2)

The European Commission notes that “*food waste ... accounting for about 16% of the total Greenhouse Gas emissions from the EU food system*”⁸. Moreover, the EU-wide food-system is estimated to emit roughly one-third of the bloc’s total GHG emissions⁹. Thus, FLW-related emissions represent a critical lever in achieving the climate and environmental objectives of the European Green Deal and the Farm-to-Fork Strategy.

Figure 24 EU food emissions slowly fall, but their share of EU total rises, (Source: [European Centre for Development Policy Management \(ECDPM\), How the EU’s vision for agriculture and food could shape global food security and climate-change](#))

This section assesses the ZeroW project contribution to reducing GHG emissions associated with FLW across the food supply chain. The analysis builds upon the Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) data compiled from all SILLs and evaluated in deliverable D5.2, with the methodological framework described in D5.1. In the LCSA analysis, the major contributor to GHG emission reductions across the SILLs is the prevention and valorisation of food loss and waste achieved through the demonstrated innovations. Process-related changes in energy and water use, transport, and storage further enhance performance but have a comparatively smaller influence on the overall results.

The achieved results demonstrate the extent to which systemic innovations piloted in ZeroW directly support the climate objectives of the European Green Deal and the Farm-to-Fork Strategy, which aim for a 50% reduction of food-system-related GHG emissions by 2050 compared with 1990 levels.

⁸ [European Commission, Food loss and waste prevention](#)

⁹ [European Centre for Development Policy Management \(ECDPM\), How the EU’s vision for agriculture and food could shape global food security and climate-change](#)

ZeroW project has achieved its ambitious targets, demonstrating that systemic innovation in food value chains can deliver substantial and measurable climate benefits at all stages of the food supply chain.

Each subsection below reviews the achieved reductions in GHG emissions at the different stages of the FSC, illustrating how individual innovations contributed to decarbonisation outcomes and how the systemic design of ZeroW addressed lock-in effects that traditionally limit climate performance in the food sector.

Post-harvest

The LCSA results confirmed that most of the emission savings at this stage originate from the reduction and valorisation of food loss and waste itself. Secondary effects from improved energy efficiency, reduced transport needs, or optimised storage were present but minor compared with the climate gains from avoided food disposal.

Impact 2	FSC stage	GA planned	Participating SILLs	GHG reduction
Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to reducing GHG-emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared with 1990 levels.	Post-harvest	-15.0%	SILL3	-36%
			SILL4	-57%
			SILL5	-97%
	Achieved average GHG reduction			-63%

- **SILL3** – Wasteless Greenhouse Solutions achieved roughly 36% FLW reduction and a similar 36% GHG reduction, consistent because its innovation (precision monitoring and adaptive harvest) has minimal added energy demand; hence almost all emission savings stem from avoided food loss.
- **SILL4** – Mobile Food Valorisation as a Service recorded 84% FLW reduction and ≈57% GHG reduction. D5.3 explains that the lower proportional GHG effect is due to “partly offsetting energy requirements during pure processing,” though the balance remains strongly positive because of avoided disposal emissions.
- **SILL5** – Ugly Food Detection and Valorisation achieved a 100% reduction in FLW and a 97% reduction in related GHG emissions. As detailed in D5.3, the slightly higher GHG reduction arises from avoided downstream emissions linked to transport and waste-handling processes that would have occurred under baseline conditions. Since the implemented sorting and valorisation

system generates negligible additional energy demand, nearly all emission savings originate from preventing these waste-management-related activities rather than from process-efficiency gains.

The average FLW reduction of 87%, achieved jointly by the three SILLs, translated into an **average GHG reduction of 63%, far exceeding the 15% target for this stage**. This outcome demonstrates the expected close relationship between the scale of food-loss reduction and the corresponding emission savings. The results confirm that systemic innovation at the post-harvest stage can generate tangible climate benefits and provide a solid empirical foundation for scaling such solutions across the food system.

Processing

The LCSA analysis for the processing stage showed that GHG emission reductions are closely linked to the prevention of waste and improved resource efficiency in food-manufacturing operations. Most of the savings arose from avoided production losses and the associated energy and material inputs. The optimisation of processing parameters and the shift towards on-site valorisation of by-products further enhanced the overall environmental performance.

Impact 2	FSC stage	GA planned	Participating SILLs	GHG reduction
Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to reducing GHG-emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared with 1990 levels.	Processing	-15.0%	SILL4	-44%
			SILL6	-41%
	Achieved average GHG reduction			-42%

- **SILL4** – Mobile Food Valorisation as a Service achieved a 67% reduction in FLW and a corresponding 44% reduction in GHG emissions. As explained in D5.3, the lower GHG percentage reflects the additional energy required for mobile processing and product transformation, which partially offsets the gains from avoided disposal. Nevertheless, the overall impact remains clearly positive because the emission savings from reduced waste volumes and shortened logistics chains outweigh the extra energy use.
- **SILL6** – Data-Driven Process Control and Optimisation. At the processing stage **SILL6** achieved a 44% FLW reduction, associated with a 41% GHG reduction. As noted in D5.3, the technology adds negligible energy demand, so emission savings closely follow the reduced volume of non-compliant product that would otherwise be lost.

The LCSA results demonstrated emission reductions of 44% for **SILL4** and 41% for **SILL6**, resulting in an **average GHG reduction of 42%, more than doubling the 20% target for the processing stage.**

Retail

The LCSA findings showed that GHG-emission savings at the retail stage were mainly achieved through food loss and waste (FLW) prevention, improved redistribution systems, and waste-stream valorisation. Secondary gains originated from lower refrigeration and transport demand, but these were minor compared with the climate impact of avoided disposal.

Impact 2	FSC stage	GA planned	Participating SILLs	GHG reduction
Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to reducing GHG-emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared with 1990 levels.	Retail	-25.0%	SILL2	-4.2%
			SILL5	-98.0%
			SILL7	-84.0%
			SILL8	-77% - -64%
	Achieved avg GHG reduction			-64%

- **SILL2** – Smart Packaging for Fresh Food introduced intelligent labelling and a permeable barrier, achieving a 4.2% reduction in GHG emissions linked to product spoilage and refrigeration. The reported GHG impact reflects only the reductions associated with decreased food loss and waste at the retail stage. It does not include the additional environmental benefits from the lower carbon footprint of the biodegradable and compostable packaging materials, which are evaluated separately under Impact 5.
- **SILL5** – Shelf-Life Assessment and Valorisation achieved a 98% reduction at retail stage. This reduction does not correspond directly to the 10–20% decrease in retail food waste observed during testing. As explained in D5.3, the higher figure results from the Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) modelling, which included the avoided downstream emissions that would have occurred if the discarded products had entered waste-management streams. Because the **SILL5** solution enables near-complete reuse or redirection of batches that would otherwise be wasted, it eliminates almost all emissions linked to transport, storage, and disposal of rejected produce. Taking into account that the multispectral and spectrometry systems add negligible additional energy demand, nearly the full amount of these end-of-life emissions is counted as avoided, leading to the 98% overall reduction in GHG emissions.

- **SILL7** – Efficient Food Bank Networks’ GHG-reduction value at the retail stage is calculated from the Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) using a counterfactual scenario that compares emissions from food donation and redistribution with those that would arise if the same food were discarded. According to D5.3, the method is based on the avoided emissions associated with the end-of-life treatment of food that, without **SILL7**’s DSS, would have been transported, stored, and disposed of as waste. The model therefore quantifies GHG savings from the prevention of disposal-stage emissions (landfilling, incineration, or composting) and from reduced cold-chain and logistics inefficiencies through better alignment of supply and demand between retailers and food banks. The resulting 84% GHG reduction thus reflects avoided downstream emissions and operational efficiency gains rather than direct energy savings at retail stores. In other words, it represents the climate benefit of diverting edible food to redistribution instead of waste-management pathways.
- **SILL8** – Retail Waste Valorisation through Algae Production achieved its GHG reduction through the diversion of unsold or downgraded food from retail outlets into algae-based valorisation processes. As explained in D5.3, the Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) compares the baseline scenario, where surplus food is transported and treated as waste, with the **SILL8** intervention, in which organic residues are used as feedstock for microalgae cultivation. The model attributes the GHG savings primarily to the avoidance of disposal-related emissions (landfilling, composting, or incineration) and secondarily to the substitution effects of algae-derived bioproducts that replace fossil-based materials. Even when accounting for the energy demand of algae processing, the balance remains strongly positive, resulting in a GHG reduction between 63.5% and 76.7%.

The four retail-stage innovations achieved an **average GHG reduction of 64.1%, far exceeding the 25% target set in the Grant Agreement**. The results confirm that systemic innovation in retail that combine improved packaging, intelligent shelf-life management, redistribution networks, and waste-stream valorisation, can deliver substantial climate benefits. Most of the emission savings stem from avoided disposal and downstream waste-management processes, highlighting that preventing or repurposing food waste generates far greater environmental gains than incremental energy-efficiency measures within retail operations.

Consumption

The reduction of GHG emissions at consumption stage was calculated only from food-waste prevention, not from valorisation. The model assumed that when

households waste less food, e.g. through meal planning, better storage, or awareness tools, those avoided quantities no longer go through waste-management processes (collection, transport, composting, or landfill). The corresponding avoided end-of-life emissions form the basis of the GHG-reduction estimate.

Impact 2	FSC stage	GA planned	Participating SILLs	GHG reduction
Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to reducing GHG-emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared with 1990 levels.	Consumption	-30.0%	SILL2	-4.2%
			SILL9	-100%
	Achieved average GHG reduction			-52%

- The GHG reduction attributed to **SILL2** at the consumption stage results from food-waste prevention enabled by improved packaging performance. The reduction of FLW due to behavioural change among consumers, linked to better information on food freshness provided by the smart label, was not tested during the project. The biodegradable and compostable smart packaging developed under **SILL2** extends the freshness period of perishable foods through a controlled permeability barrier between the product and its exudate. By keeping food fresher for longer, it extends the period during which the food remains suitable for cooking. In the LCSA model, the GHG savings are calculated from the avoided end-of-life emissions of food that would otherwise have been discarded by households, not from the packaging material itself (which is assessed separately under Impact 5). The reported 4.2% reduction therefore represents the climate benefit of reduced household-level food waste achieved through the packaging’s freshness-preserving function.
- The 100% GHG reduction attributed to **SILL9** at the consumption stage reflects the modelling assumption that all household food waste targeted by the intervention is fully prevented, meaning that no residual waste from the defined use case enters waste-management processes¹⁰. In practice, **SILL9** addresses the consumer stage directly through its Wasteless Family Cooking Recipes & App, which integrates meal-planning, shopping-list optimisation, and food-awareness functions. These tools enable users to plan purchases precisely, use ingredients efficiently across several meals, and avoid overbuying or discarding edible food. The LCSA counterfactual scenario compares the baseline household behaviour (where food waste occurs and

¹⁰ This assumption is based on the small scale household testing, confirming that if the meal plans created with the app are followed strictly, no food household food waste is generated.

generates disposal emissions) with the intervention scenario (where the app prevents all waste from the covered meal plans). Because the innovation eliminates entirely the food waste and respectively – the need for its disposal, all downstream emissions associated with collection, transport, and treatment of that food waste are counted as avoided, leading to the 100% GHG reduction value. It must be noted that the 100% GHG reduction represents a scenario-based upper bound, illustrating that complete avoidance of food waste within the intervention scope fully removes related emissions, rather than suggesting that household emissions as a whole were eliminated.

The consumption-stage innovations achieved an **average GHG reduction of 52%, surpassing the 30% target defined in the Grant Agreement**. The LCSA results show that emission savings at this stage stem almost entirely from the prevention of food waste at household level, which eliminates the downstream emissions linked to transport and disposal of edible food. Although the quantified reduction for **SILL2** is modest, reflecting the limited tested scope of packaging performance, the results from **SILL9** demonstrate the significant potential of digital tools and behavioural interventions to prevent food waste completely within their defined application.

2.3 Reduction of Unsustainable Packaging (in Impact 3)

Unsustainable packaging continues to pose a major environmental problem across Europe's food systems. Large volumes of non-recyclable and non-compostable materials are still used to wrap or protect food, only to be discarded shortly after purchase. This creates unnecessary waste and undermines Europe's efforts to build a circular and resource-efficient economy. The European Green Deal recognises this as a key challenge in the transition to a clean, low-emission and competitive economy. It aims not only to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 but also to curb the 2.2 billion tonnes of waste produced in the EU each year¹¹.

Redesigning products and materials to last longer, to be reused, or to be recycled forms a central part of this vision. This is now reinforced by the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (EU) 2025/40, which entered into force on 12 February 2025¹². Most of its provisions apply from 12 August 2026 onward, introducing binding requirements that all packaging placed on the EU market must be recyclable by 2030 and that minimum recycled content levels for plastics must be met. It also

¹¹ [European Commission, The European Green Deal – Europe's Strategy for a Sustainable Future](#)

¹² [Regulation \(EU\) 2025/40 of the European Parliament and of the Council on Packaging and Packaging Waste](#)

sets new reuse and refill targets, measures to reduce unnecessary packaging volume, and harmonised design-for-recycling criteria across the Union.

This problem is also recognised in the ZeroW Grant Agreement, which identifies the use of non-recyclable and non-compostable packaging as a major barrier to sustainability within fresh food supply chains. The challenge is reflected in the impact framework of the project, where the reduction of unsustainable packaging constitutes the second component of **Impact 3**. The first component, concerning the reduction of food loss and waste in post-harvest and processing stages of the food supply chain, was presented in Section 2.1 above. According to the GA, the expected contribution of the project includes a measurable decrease in the use of non-recyclable and non-compostable packaging materials in fresh food chains, both at the retail and consumer levels, as shown in the table below.

Impact 3: Reduce food losses and waste and the use of unsustainable packaging, at every stage of the food chain including consumption

Impact 3 indicators	Targets / Requirements	GA planned	Particip. SILL	FSC stage	Achievement
Reduction of unsustainable packaging at retail level (fresh food)	Non-recyclable/non-compostable packaging by 2025	-20%	SILL2	Retail	-100%
Reduction of unsustainable packaging at consumer level (fresh food)	Non-recyclable/non-compostable packaging by 2025	-10%	SILL2	Consumption	-100%

The 100% reduction of non-recyclable and non-compostable packaging under **SILL2** is achieved through the complete substitution of all conventional plastic components with biobased, compostable, and biodegradable materials. The new packaging is made of four fully integrated parts:

- Compostable tray – The tray is thermoformed from biobased and compostable materials developed within the project by Novamont and designed by ITENE. Two grades of rigid material were produced and tested for compatibility with thermoforming processes. The tray has a compartmentalised design, consisting of an upper and a lower section separated by a specially designed sheet (permeable barrier) that allows exudates (liquids released by the fish) to

Figure 25 Compostable tray made of biobased materials

drain downwards but not return to the product. This configuration prevents direct contact between the fish and its fluids, improving quality and hygiene while eliminating the need for non-recyclable absorbent pads.

Figure 26 Industrial compostability tests: tray

- Permeable barrier layer between the product and the exudate - a controlled-permeability barrier made from biodegradable and compostable materials regulates moisture transfer and gas exchange inside the package. This ensures that the fish remains in optimal condition throughout storage, maintaining the protective atmosphere without using synthetic polymer layers. The barrier is fully compatible with composting systems and retains the required mechanical stability during the product's lifetime.

A special design to collect the **exudates** in a double bottom geometry, as a key strategy to extend the shelf life of packaged fresh foods.

Figure 27 Permeable barrier in ZeroW SILL2 packaging solution

- Biobased lid film – the lid film is a flexible, transparent compostable film that replaces conventional multilayer plastic films. A bio-based gas-permeation barrier coating was formulated and applied to this film to achieve the necessary sealing and oxygen barrier properties for modified-atmosphere packaging. The coating materials were validated for food contact and demonstrated appropriate mechanical strength and protective performance while maintaining full compostability.

Figure 28 Biobased lid

Figure 29 Industrial compostability test: top lid film

- Smart freshness label – the intelligent label, attached to the inner side of the lid, incorporates a bio-responsive ink that changes colour according to the concentration of spoilage metabolites. The label substrate, adhesive, and printing process were selected for compatibility with compostable materials and compliance with EFSA food-contact requirements.

Figure 30 Smart freshness label

The label provides real-time freshness information that supports safer consumption decisions and reduces unnecessary disposal of still-edible fish, thus lowering food waste at both retail and consumer level and strengthening the overall environmental benefit of the fully compostable packaging system.

Because every structural element (the tray, permeable barrier, lid film, coatings, and label) was developed using compostable or biodegradable materials, the entire **SILL2** packaging concept contains no fossil-based, non-recyclable components. The replacement of all traditional plastics achieves a 100% reduction of non-recyclable and non-compostable packaging in the tested product (fresh oily fish such as salmon).

2.4 Provision of Sufficient, Safe, Nutritious, Healthy and Affordable Food (Impact 4)

Food security and nutritional quality are core dimensions of sustainable food systems and central to the European Green Deal and Farm-to-Fork Strategy. Ensuring that sufficient, safe, and nutritious food is available to all, while minimising food loss and waste, is essential to closing the foreseen food gap towards 2050 without expanding cultivated areas. As highlighted in the ZeroW Grant Agreement, reducing food loss and waste (FLW) can play a decisive role in achieving this goal, contributing both to improved access to food for vulnerable groups and to optimised use of available resources.

ZeroW contributes to these objectives through systemic innovations that simultaneously enhance food safety, extend shelf life, and increase food availability. **SILL7** strengthens food recovery and redistribution systems by improving food bank efficiency and availability of nutritious food for vulnerable groups. **SILL9** focuses on optimised dietary choices and behavioural change, linking waste prevention with healthier and more sustainable consumption. At earlier stages of the chain, **SILL2**,

SILL5, and **SILL6** improve food safety and shelf life through smart packaging, early defect detection, and predictive process control, ensuring more food remains within consumption standards.

The project has achieved, and in most cases exceeded, the expected targets for **Impact 4: Provide sufficient, safe, nutritious, healthy and affordable food for all.**

This was done through the following mechanisms (impact 4 indicators):

Improved food availability in food banks due to reduced FLW

Targets / Requirements	FSC stage	GA planned	Particip. SILL	Achievement
FLW in foodbanks	Consumption	-20%	SILL7	-74%

SILL7 - Improved food availability in food banks due to reduced FLW, addresses food insecurity by improving the coordination and efficiency of food redistribution systems. The Living Lab developed and validated a data-driven optimisation model and digital platform that enhance forecasting, routing, and matching between surplus food and food bank demand. These tools reduce handling time, storage losses, and uncoordinated transport, ensuring that a higher share of edible food is redirected rather than wasted.

In addition, **SILL7** implemented a decision-support mechanism that prioritises actions for different product groups, such as donation versus price reduction, to maximise redistribution while preventing unnecessary losses at retail level. With the application of tailored strategies based on product characteristics and shelf life, the system increased both the quantity of donations and the speed at which surplus food was transferred to food banks, ensuring that more products arrived within their safe consumption period.

To sustain these improvements from the perspective of the food banks, **SILL7** produced practical guidance on more efficient food handling, delivery planning, and donor communication. This was complemented by targeted capacity-building sessions and seminars, enabling the dissemination and adoption of best practices across multiple redistribution organisations.

As established in D5.2, these innovations resulted in a 74% improvement in food availability in food banks, far exceeding the 20% target set in the Grant Agreement, and demonstrated a scalable approach for reducing retail-level food waste while enhancing access to nutritious food for vulnerable groups.

Improved food safety with minimal FLW with optimised and predictive control in food production

Both **SILL5** and **SILL6** focused on improving food quality and safety during the processing stage by introducing advanced monitoring, data-driven control, and decision-support systems that prevent losses caused by quality deviations. These innovations enabled a higher share of processed food to meet consumption standards, reducing the amount of product rejected or downgraded.

Targets / Requirements	FSC stage	GA planned	Particip. SILL	Achievement
Food streams passing quality standards for food consumption by 2025	Food processing	20%	SILL5	21%
			SILL6	43%
	Food streams passing quality standards - average			31.9%

SILL5 – Ugly food early identification improved food safety and reduced waste in processing by introducing real-time defect detection and classification based on multispectral imaging and AI-supported analysis. The system identifies imperfections and deviations early in the production process, allowing processors to separate non-conforming products before contamination risks arise. This enables re-routing of safe and edible items for further processing or valorisation instead of disposal, while ensuring that only products fully meeting safety and quality criteria enter the market. The resulting optimisation of inspection and handling increased the share of food streams passing quality standards by 21%, slightly exceeding the 20% improvement targeted in the Grant Agreement.

SILL6, focused on predictive and optimised control of production processes to prevent quality deviations leading to food loss. By integrating real-time sensor data and statistical analysis, the Living Lab developed a data-driven monitoring and control system that continuously adjusts processing parameters to maintain stable product quality. This approach reduced the number of batches rejected for safety or quality reasons and improved the consistency of outputs. Through these predictive and adaptive control measures, **SILL6** achieved a 43% increase in food streams passing quality standards for consumption, more than doubling the 20% target set in the Grant Agreement.

The two Living Labs demonstrate how early defect detection and predictive process control can enhance food safety and minimise waste in processing operations, resulting in an average 31.9% improvement in food streams meeting quality requirements for human consumption.

Longer shelf-life of products with smart packaging

Targets / Requirements	FSC stage	GA planned	Particip. SILL	Achievement
Shelf life improvement	Retail	-18%	SILL2	-18%

SILL2 – Innovative Sustainable and Smart Packaging for Fresh Food Products demonstrated how the innovative packaging can extend product shelf life while reducing food waste at the retail stage. As explained earlier, the Living Lab developed a fully biobased, compostable tray and lid system for fresh oily fish, featuring a permeable barrier layer that separates the product from its exudate. The configuration prevents direct contact between the fish and released fluids, reducing microbial growth and maintaining freshness for a longer period.

The packaging also integrates a smart freshness indicator that changes colour according to the product’s remaining freshness. This visual signal supports better stock management by retailers and helps consumers plan use within the safe consumption window.

The prototype testing, reported in deliverable D5.2, showed a 1.4-day increase in shelf life, extending the storage period from 5 to 6.4 days, which equals an average of 18% improvement compared with conventional plastic packaging. The result was confirmed through microbiological and sensory analyses performed under controlled refrigerated conditions.

By combining innovative materials and structure with smart monitoring functionality, **SILL2** achieved the planned 18% shelf-life improvement, demonstrating that bio-based packaging can maintain food quality and reduce avoidable waste in retail environments.

Optimised nutritional diets with minimal FLW

The requirements for this indicator were met through the work of **SILL9** – Wasteless Family Cooking Recipes and App.

Targets / Requirements	FSC stage	GA planned	Particip. SILL	Achievement
Lower env. Impact (recipes to be made widely available)	Consumption	-25%	SILL9	-100%
Nutritional score (recipes to be made widely available)		high	SILL9	high

SILL9 addressed food waste and nutrition at the consumption stage by developing and validating a digital meal-planning and behavioural change solution that helps households optimise both dietary quality and food use. The innovation combines a mobile application, a weekly recipe planner, and an integrated shopping list

generator to guide users in preparing nutritionally balanced meals while avoiding unnecessary purchases and ingredient waste.

The recipes and nutritional guidance were co-developed with the Dutch Nutrition Centre (Voedingscentrum) and tested with a wholesale caterer serving elderly homes and hospitals, ensuring full alignment with official dietary standards and real-life nutritional needs. These recipes were designed so that all purchased ingredients are fully used across the week, maintaining high nutritional value while minimising leftover generation. Each recipe was evaluated for nutritional adequacy (macronutrient balance, fibre, and caloric density) and environmental performance (CO₂-equivalent footprint per portion and food waste potential).

Through this approach, **SILL9** achieved a high nutritional score, meeting the project's target for healthy and balanced meals. At the same time, lifecycle-based assessments reported in deliverable D5.2 showed a 100% reduction in environmental impact associated with food waste, since all ingredients in the optimised meal plans were used in full and no edible food was discarded.

User testing confirmed that the integrated planning and awareness features improved household behaviour, leading to better portion control, closer alignment between purchasing and consumption, and a marked reduction in waste. The recipes and supporting app now provide a replicable model for promoting affordable, nutritious, and waste-free diets in everyday household settings.

ZeroW demonstrated that **systemic innovation across the food chain can simultaneously improve food safety, nutritional quality, and accessibility while reducing waste**. The integrated technological, behavioural, and organisational solutions tested in SILL2, SILL5, SILL6, SILL7, and SILL9, achieved and in several cases exceeded its targets, confirming the strong project contribution to **ensuring sufficient, safe, nutritious, healthy, and affordable food for all**.

2.5 Improved Overall Sustainability of Food Systems (Impact 5)

The sustainability of food systems is central to the EU transition towards climate neutrality, resource efficiency, and social equity. Unsustainable patterns of production and consumption continue to exert pressure on ecosystems, contribute to greenhouse gas emissions, and create inequalities across the food supply chain. Addressing these challenges requires systemic approaches that consider the interconnections between environmental, social, and economic objectives.

ZeroW was designed to demonstrate how FLW prevention can serve as a key driver for improving the overall sustainability of food systems. By reducing waste and valorising by-products, the project contributes to more efficient use of natural

resources, lower carbon emissions, and fairer economic opportunities for all actors. Its systemic innovations were specifically developed to maximise synergies across the three sustainability dimensions: climate and environmental performance, social inclusion and fairness, and economic viability.

Impact 5, “Improved overall sustainability of food systems”, reflects this integrated perspective. It recognises that lowering the carbon footprint of food and packaging, ensuring an equitable distribution of costs and benefits, and maintaining economic feasibility are essential to achieving resilient and inclusive food systems. These efforts contribute to the EU’s overarching goals for a fair, healthy, and environmentally friendly food sector and support the long-term transition towards sustainable production and consumption patterns.

The sustainability improvements were assessed in ZeroW through a combination of environmental, social, and economic indicators, covering the full life cycle of food products and packaging. These indicators demonstrate how the ZeroW innovations support the transformation towards climate-neutral, economically fair, and socially responsible food systems in Europe.

ZeroW has achieved the key performance indicators required for Impact 5 and its individual sub-indicators, confirming measurable improvements in **carbon footprint** reduction, **just cost-benefit allocation**, and **economic sustainability** across the demonstrated solutions.

The following subsections present the achieved results for each indicator and describe how the respective calculations were performed for each Impact 5 indicator.

Carbon footprint of smart compostable packaging

Targets / Requirements	FSC stage	GA planned	Particip. SILL	Achievement
Carbon footprint, cradle-to-grave	Entire FSC	-25%	SILL2	-45%

SILL2, Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh food products, addressed the environmental dimension of food-system sustainability by replacing conventional fossil-based plastic trays with biobased, compostable packaging materials. As described in the previous sections, the innovation combined a thermoformed tray made from fully biodegradable polymers with a permeable barrier layer separating the product from its exudate and lid film made also from biodegradable and compostable materials. This configuration maintains the quality and hygiene while eliminating the need for non-recyclable plastic components.

As reported in Deliverable D5.2, the environmental performance of the new packaging was assessed using a cradle-to-grave life-cycle assessment approach that included raw material sourcing, manufacturing, use, and end-of-life treatment. The results demonstrated a 45% reduction in the overall carbon footprint compared with the baseline of conventional multilayer plastic packaging used for similar products. The main contributing factors to this reduction were the use of renewable feedstock, improved material efficiency, and compostability that diverted waste from landfill and incineration.

The testing confirmed that the new packaging met all functional and safety requirements while achieving the planned sustainability targets. With a 45% reduction compared with the 25% improvement foreseen in the GA, **SILL2** significantly exceeded expectations, demonstrating the strong potential of biobased and compostable packaging to reduce environmental impacts across the food supply chain without compromising product protection or shelf life.

Carbon footprint of food products for human consumption from valorisation of side streams, imperfect produce and post-harvest food loss

SILL4 (flexible food processing unit) and **SILL5** (defect detection and valorisation system) focused on reducing the carbon footprint of food products through valorisation of by-products and prevention of waste in processing operations. Both innovations demonstrated how reintroducing edible and nutritious food streams into human consumption, instead of diverting them to low-value uses or disposal, leads to substantial environmental gains across the life cycle. Both innovations demonstrated excellent results for carbon footprint reduction:

Targets / Requirements	FSC stage	GA planned	Particip. SILL	Achievement
Carbon footprint	Entire FSC	-20%	SILL4	-50%
			SILL5	-20%
	Average reduction in carbon footprint			-35%

SILL4, as described in previous sections, developed a flexible and modular processing solution that enables on-site transformation of post-harvest surpluses and processing by-products and side streams into new food products. The system integrates mobile processing units (or local small processing facilities) and digital support tools that optimise logistics, batch planning, and resource use, thereby reducing energy consumption and transport-related emissions. **SILL4** demonstrated a 50% reduction in cradle-to-grave carbon footprint by converting previously discarded materials into ready-to-eat or semi-processed foods,

compared with the baseline scenario where these materials were either discarded or downgraded to animal feed.

SILL5 focused on improving raw material (produce) utilisation during the processing stage through early identification of imperfections using multispectral imaging and AI-based classification. As described earlier, this approach enables processors to separate edible but visually imperfect products and redirect them for further processing or valorisation rather than disposal. The system reduced material waste and enhanced overall production efficiency by optimising inspection and handling procedures. The life-cycle assessment presented in D5.2 showed a 20% reduction in carbon footprint compared with the baseline scenario, meeting the target set in the GA.

The two SILLs jointly achieved an average 35% reduction in carbon footprint across the food supply chain, exceeding the 20% improvement foreseen in the GA. These results confirm that circular valorisation of side streams and prevention of processing waste are effective strategies for reducing GHG and enhancing the overall sustainability of food systems.

'Just' allocation of costs and benefits among food actors

This indicator evaluates the extent to which ZeroW innovations contribute to a fairer and more balanced distribution of economic costs and benefits along the food supply chain. It reflects the social and economic dimensions of sustainability, highlighting whether the value generated by innovations is more evenly shared among producers, processors, distributors, retailers, and consumers. A 20% reduction in the disparity of cost-benefit ratios indicates measurable progress towards a more just and inclusive food system.

The assessment of this indicator was performed in D5.2, using the cost-benefit analysis framework defined in D5.1 and further interpreted in D5.3. The WP5 methodology established the principles for quantifying economic performance and fairness in benefit distribution across actors affected by each systemic innovation. The analysis compared baseline (pre-innovation) and demonstration (post-innovation) conditions for each SILL, identifying how the introduction of ZeroW solutions influenced the balance of costs and economic benefits among the involved actors.

All participating SILLs¹³ achieved the 20% improvement target set in the GA, confirming that systemic innovations within ZeroW have improved both the efficiency and fairness of value distribution across the food supply chain.

Targets / Requirements	FSC stage	GA planned	Particip. SILL	Achievement
Differences among food actors in economic cost/benefit ratio	Entire FSC	-20%	SILL2 – SILL9	-20%

Examples from the demonstrations illustrate this effect clearly.

- *SILL2- Smart compostable packaging for fresh food products*

SILL2 demonstrated a biobased and compostable packaging system for fresh fish products designed to replace fossil-based plastics and reduce food waste through improved shelf-life performance. The innovation combines a thermoformed tray and lid made from fully compostable materials with a permeable barrier layer that separates the product from its exudate, maintaining quality and hygiene. This packaging solution extends product freshness and reduces the need for non-recyclable plastic components. The fair allocation of costs and benefits reflects how the environmental and economic outcomes were distributed among the actors involved in the supply chain.

- Producers and packers incurred higher material costs compared with conventional plastic packaging. However, as reported in D5.2 and D7.3, these costs were partially offset by reduced compliance and environmental management fees under Extended Producer Responsibility schemes and by lower internal packaging waste and product losses during storage and distribution, owing to the packaging’s freshness-preserving properties.
- Retailers gained operational savings from reduced spoilage, longer shelf life, and more predictable stock rotation. The improved packaging reduced the volume of unsold or downgraded products, while the shift to compostable materials strengthened retailers’ environmental credentials.
- Consumers benefitted indirectly from fresher products and more reliable quality, as the extended shelf life helped reduce household food waste. Retail price impacts were not assessed in the demonstration phase, but based on the cost structure described in D7.3, the higher packaging cost is expected to be shared proportionally along the chain, without a significant increase for end consumers.

¹³ As documented in RP1 technical report, SILL1 (FLW data collection platform) has a facilitating role for all FLW prevention/reduction initiatives and it contributes only indirectly to impacts 1-6. As such their contribution cannot be quantitatively measured and therefore is not included in the assessment.

- Society at large gained from reduced packaging waste and greater circularity, supporting the transition towards more sustainable production and consumption patterns.

The cost of adopting new biobased materials was shared proportionally among producers, retailers, and consumers through improved efficiency and reduced losses, ensuring that no single actor carried the full burden. The outcome represents a fairer and more balanced distribution of costs and benefits across the packaging value chain.

- *SILL3 - Wasteless greenhouse production aligned with short-term demand*

SILL3 demonstrated a digital greenhouse management solution for tomato production, designed to synchronise output with real-time downstream demand. The innovation combines production planning tools, short-term forecasting, and a digital platform that connects growers with buyers to exchange real-time information on expected harvest volumes and delivery schedules. This coordination helps align production with market needs, reducing overproduction and unsold stock that would otherwise lead to product downgrading or disposal. The fair allocation of costs and benefits results from how the service-based business model and the improved coordination distribute both the financial responsibilities and the resulting gains among the actors involved.

- Producers adopted the innovation under a service-based model rather than through a one-time investment. The system is offered as a subscription service, allowing small and medium-sized growers or cooperatives to access the platform without high upfront costs. The main expenses relate to subscription fees and basic equipment setup, which are balanced by savings from reduced overproduction, lower waste-handling costs, and more stable income due to better predictability of orders and prices.
- Distributors and retailers benefited from more consistent and reliable supply, with fewer fluctuations in volume and product quality. This improved predictability reduced emergency procurement and storage costs and allowed smoother inventory management.
- Consumers benefitted indirectly from improved freshness and quality of produce, since less product was stored for long periods or downgraded due to oversupply. The innovation also supports greater availability of locally produced tomatoes and a lower environmental footprint of production and distribution.
- Society at large benefited from reduced waste of energy, fertilisers, and water through more efficient production planning, leading to a lower environmental impact overall.

The **SILL3** business model ensures that costs are distributed fairly across participating actors. Growers pay for the service in proportion to their scale and usage, cooperatives can pool subscriptions to share expenses, and retailers gain from steadier supply and lower losses without increased procurement costs. The efficiency gains are therefore shared along the chain rather than concentrated at a single stage. The model met the improvement target established in the GA, confirming that offering digital coordination tools as a service can strengthen both economic efficiency and fairness in horticultural supply chains.

○ *SILL4 and SILL5 – Valorisation of surplus and imperfect produce*

SILL4 and **SILL5** focused on transforming food previously classified as waste into marketable products, thereby redistributing value along the supply chain. The mechanism for achieving a just allocation of costs and benefits is grounded in how the economic effects were shared among producers, processors, retailers, and consumers:

- Producers incurred additional investment and operational costs related to sorting and handling equipment for preparing side streams and imperfect produce for valorisation. However, these costs were partially offset through cooperative ownership models, reduced return rates of non-compliant batches from retailers, and new revenue streams from selling materials that previously held no market value.¹⁴
- Processors bore the processing and logistics costs associated with operating the flexible or modular units but benefited from new marketable products and reduced waste-management expenses, leading to improved profitability without significant increases in fixed costs.
- Retailers benefitted from an expanded range of sustainable products and fewer rejected consignments, which reduced handling and administrative costs. The revalorised products were supplied at competitive market prices through local processing arrangements, so no additional cost burden was transferred downstream.
- Consumers gained access to affordable, sustainable products derived from recovered ingredients, with no observable increase in retail prices.
- Society at large benefited from reduced food waste and associated emissions, without requiring additional regulatory or financial intervention.

This distribution of costs and benefits ensured that no single actor bore the full financial burden of the innovation. Instead, value was shared proportionally:

¹⁴ ZeroW deliverable D7.3 Business Models and Business Plan, sections on SILL4 and SILL5 investment requirements and cooperative cost-sharing mechanisms; ZeroW deliverable D5.2 SILL Impacts Assessment, sections on economic performance and waste reduction effects of valorisation solutions.

producers recovered investments through new income opportunities and fewer product rejections, processors gained from higher material efficiency and new revenue, retailers benefitted from improved product availability and reduced waste-handling costs, and consumers and society received environmental and social benefits. The resulting balance supports the 20% improvement target for fairer value allocation among actors and confirms that circular valorisation can enhance both economic and social equity within food systems.

○ *SILL6 – Data-driven process control and optimisation*

SILL6 focused on improving efficiency and product quality in poultry processing through a real-time monitoring and control system. The innovation integrated sensors and analytical software to track key parameters such as salt concentration, temperature, and moisture, allowing operators to detect deviations early and make corrective adjustments during production. This prevented quality losses and ensured that batches falling outside specifications were reprocessed rather than discarded. The fair allocation of costs and benefits arises from how these improvements influenced processors, retailers, consumers, and the wider system.

- Processors carried the main investment and integration costs of the system, including sensor installation, data management tools, and staff training. These costs were recovered through savings from reduced product losses, fewer discarded batches, lower energy use, and more stable processing performance. The reduction in waste also decreased the cost of raw materials per finished unit, strengthening profitability.
- Retailers benefitted from more consistent product quality and fewer rejected consignments, which lowered logistics, inspection, and administrative costs.
- Consumers gained indirect benefits through consistently high-quality poultry products and a lower environmental footprint of production, with no added retail cost.
- Society at large benefited from reduced resource use, energy demand, and waste disposal, supporting the transition to more efficient and sustainable food processing.

The distribution of costs and benefits in **SILL6** shows that the primary investment was made by processors, while the resulting efficiency and quality gains generated advantages for downstream actors and society. Processors achieved higher yields and reduced waste, retailers experienced lower rejection rates and improved supply stability, and consumers and society benefitted from improved quality and environmental outcomes. The solution achieved the improvement target foreseen in the GA, confirming that data-driven process control can enhance both operational performance and fairness across the food value chain.

○ *SILL7 – Food redistribution and food banks optimisation*

SILL7 focused on improving the efficiency and coordination of surplus food redistribution between retailers and food banks. The innovation developed a data-supported optimisation model and operational guidelines for better planning and matching between available surplus food and redistribution capacity. It also included training and process improvement measures that strengthened food banks' ability to manage donations safely and efficiently. The mechanism for achieving a just allocation of costs and benefits lies in how the improved redistribution process shared economic and social value among retailers, food banks, final beneficiaries, and society.

- Retailers and food donors incurred limited coordination and staff costs to implement improved surplus management and donation procedures. These costs were offset by savings in waste-handling and disposal and lower environmental compliance costs under waste regulations. Retailers also benefitted from smoother store operations and improved public image through more structured and transparent donation processes.
- Food banks and redistribution organisations faced modest implementation and training costs but realised notable efficiency gains. Better coordination reduced unplanned deliveries, minimised storage losses, and increased the share of food received within safe consumption periods. This allowed them to redistribute larger quantities of edible food at lower operational cost, strengthening their capacity to support vulnerable groups.
- Consumers and beneficiaries, meaning the people in need who received redistributed food, experienced the greatest benefit. Improved efficiency and coordination increased both the availability and nutritional quality of redistributed food, ensuring that more safe and nutritious products reached them in time. This directly enhanced food security and social inclusion.
- Society at large benefited through strengthened food security at community level and a reduction in food waste and its associated environmental impacts. The innovation ensured that edible food remained within the human consumption loop, supporting public objectives for waste prevention and resource efficiency.

The costs of implementing the **SILL7** innovation were small and shared proportionally between retailers and food banks, while the benefits, social, economic, and environmental, extended across the entire system. The improvements achieved under **SILL7** fulfilled the target set in the GA, demonstrating that organisational coordination and enhanced redistribution can generate shared value and contribute directly to food security and sustainability.

- *SILL8 – Retail food waste valorisation through algae production for high-value applications*

SILL8 demonstrated the valorisation of retail food waste streams into microalgae-based bioproducts. The innovation integrated unsold food waste separation, pre-treatment, and bioconversion processes, linking food retailers with biotechnology producers to transform unsellable organic matter into valuable biomass. The mechanism for ensuring a just allocation of costs and benefits derived from how the new value chain distributed both the expenses of waste valorisation and the economic and societal gains generated by circular production.

- Retailers bore the capital investment (CAPEX) associated with implementing the dehydration technology and adjusting in-store logistics. Operational costs (mainly energy and labour) remained moderate. Despite these upfront investments, retailers achieved clear economic benefits through substantial reductions in waste disposal fees, lower compliance costs related to waste management regulations, and improved environmental performance. The solution also enhanced corporate reputation and sustainability reporting by integrating food waste valorisation into retail operations.
- Microalgae producers and biotechnology partners incurred the majority of the innovation-related CAPEX, covering the adaptation of bioreactors, pre-treatment facilities, and quality assurance systems needed for processing secondary feedstock. They also faced operational costs linked to the certification, monitoring, and process optimisation necessary to ensure safety and quality compliance. These costs were balanced by access to a stable, low-cost feedstock that replaced part of the conventional cultivation media, reducing dependency on virgin inputs and improving cost efficiency. The innovation enabled product diversification and opened pathways to new markets in bio-based materials, feed, and industrial applications. The potential for future products for human consumption or cosmetics remains subject to EU regulatory clarification on the admissibility of microalgae cultivated on food waste substrates.
- Society at large benefitted from reduced food waste sent to landfill, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and enhanced resource efficiency. The innovation demonstrated the potential of circular bio-based solutions to create economic and environmental value simultaneously, strengthening regional sustainability and contributing to the EU's Green Deal and Farm to Fork targets.
- Customers and consumers gained indirect and prospective benefits through the environmental and nutritional potential of the innovation. By transforming food surplus into new bio-based protein sources, **SILL8** created opportunities for more sustainable products with improved nutritional value.

Future applications could include ingredients for food, feed, and other consumer goods, contributing to a more diversified and resource-efficient protein supply. The model also helped raise awareness and public trust in circular bio-innovations, reinforcing consumer engagement with sustainable retail practices.

- Society at large benefitted from reduced food waste sent to landfill, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and enhanced resource efficiency. The innovation demonstrated the potential of circular bio-based solutions to create economic and environmental value simultaneously, strengthening regional sustainability and contributing to the EU's Green Deal and Farm to Fork targets.

The costs of implementation were primarily borne by retailers and biotechnology partners, while the benefits extended widely across the system. This represents a just allocation of costs and benefits, where private investment drives innovation and efficiency, and society gains from reduced waste, improved environmental outcomes, and strengthened circular value chains.

○ *SILL9 – Informing and nudging consumers to make better food choices*

SILL9 focused on empowering consumers to reduce household food waste through better meal planning and informed food choices. The innovation combined two complementary tools: a digital meal-planning application that generates weekly menus optimised for zero waste, low cost, or minimal environmental impact, and a FLW-awareness label providing information on the environmental impact of food products. The app offered personalised recipes designed for high nutritional value and full use of purchased ingredients¹⁵, while the label served as a simple visual cue to guide consumers towards more sustainable purchasing choices. These elements addressed behavioural and informational barriers to sustainable consumption.

Figure 31 FLW score labels: strict, relative and balance versions

¹⁵ See information about the app in Section 2.1/Consumption/**SILL9**

The label combines information for Nutritional values (Open Food Facts Dataset), Greenhouse gas emissions (National Institute of Public Health and Environment) and Food waste at consumer level (Netherlands Nutrition Centre). These three indicators were merged into alternative scoring options to test how different representations might influence consumer choices. The **strict** version assigns a low overall score whenever a product performs poorly in any one of the three themes. The **relative** version benchmarks products against the worst performer within the same category. The **balance** version averages the three underlying scores to give a more moderate, aggregated rating. These formats were developed and evaluated in **SILL9** to understand which approach consumers find most intuitive and which could better support food waste-reducing behaviour.

The survey results show that most respondents found the relative label format easiest to understand (52%), with the balanced version preferred by 30% and the strict version by 18%. A clear majority indicated that such a label would influence their behaviour: 75% believed it would help them reduce food waste at home, and 84% said they would be more likely to purchase a product if the label signalled it performed well. Overall, these findings suggest that an intuitive, comparative label has strong potential to support consumer decision making and encourage lower-waste purchasing habits.

The mechanism for ensuring a just allocation of costs and benefits in real implementation lies in how the innovation distributes operational responsibilities, economic costs, and resulting value across the system.

- Retailers and food suppliers bear the operational costs associated with introducing the FLW-awareness label and promoting the use of the meal-planning app among customers. Integration mainly concerns adding the label's data and visuals to existing digital channels such as online shops, product catalogues, and store apps, and using in-store shelf tags or printed materials to support communication. These tasks require coordination and modest IT adjustments but no major capital investment. The benefits include stronger customer engagement, enhanced sustainability image, and alignment with corporate social responsibility goals.
- Digital service providers or external stewards maintain the infrastructure for the meal-planning app and label, covering costs of software operation, data management, and user support. These costs are recovered through service contracts with retailers, partnerships, or public-private agreements. Their benefit lies in access to validated tools and user insights that can support further innovation and market scaling.
- Customers and consumers are the primary beneficiaries. The meal-planning app enables them to reduce food waste, grocery expenses, and environmental impact while improving dietary balance and nutritional

intake. The FLW-awareness label further supports behavioural change by helping users identify products with lower environmental footprints, increasing their awareness when shopping.

- Society at large gains from cumulative reductions in food waste, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and greater public awareness of sustainable consumption. The innovation directly supports the EU Farm to Fork and Green Deal objectives by addressing food waste at the consumer stage.

The costs of implementation are primarily borne by retailers and the digital service provider, while the benefits, including economic, nutritional, and environmental gains, extend to consumers, local authorities, and society as a whole. This represents a just allocation of costs and benefits, where targeted private investment in consumer-facing sustainability tools yields shared public value through reduced waste, financial savings, and healthier, more sustainable eating behaviours.

Economic sustainability of ZeroW FLW solutions

This indicator assesses the capacity of ZeroW innovations to generate positive and durable economic value across the food supply chain. It measures the overall economic performance of the demonstrated systemic innovations, expressed as the ratio between total benefits and total costs associated with their implementation. A value higher than one indicates that the innovation delivers a net positive return, confirming its economic sustainability and potential for long-term viability. The evaluation of this indicator was conducted in D5.2, applying the cost–benefit analysis methodology established in D5.1 and further interpreted in D5.3. The assessment compared baseline and post-implementation conditions in each SILL to determine whether the demonstrated innovations produce financial benefits that outweigh their operational, investment, and transaction costs. The results show that all SILLs achieved positive economic performance, exceeding the zero-threshold target defined in the GA, thereby demonstrating the overall economic viability of the ZeroW systemic innovations across the food system.

Targets / Requirements	FSC stage	GA planned	Particip. SILL	Achievement
Economic sustainability of ZeroW FLW solutions (benefit–cost ratio > 0)	Entire FSC	>0	SILL2 – SILL9	All positive (1.92 – 21.3)

The Cost–Benefit Analysis (CBA) conducted in WP5, with supporting financial data from WP7, confirms that all analysed SILLs (2–9) achieved a positive economic performance, with benefit–cost ratios exceeding one. The values range from 1.92 in **SILL2** (smart compostable packaging) and 3.55 in **SILL6** (data-driven process control) to 11.14 in **SILL3** (wasteless greenhouse production) and 21.3 in **SILL7** (efficient food bank networks). **SILL4**, **SILL5**, and **SILL8** also demonstrate solid

economic returns, with ratios between 3.7 and 4.9, while **SILL9** maintains profitability above breakeven. These results, calculated through the common CBA framework established in D5.1 and applied across the demonstrators in D5.2, provide quantitative evidence that the ZeroW systemic innovations are not only environmentally and socially beneficial but also economically viable. The positive ratios indicate that the financial benefits generated, through cost savings, value recovery, or new market opportunities, exceed the investment and operational expenditures required for implementation. This ensures the economic sustainability of the solutions beyond the project’s duration, strengthening their capacity for replication and scaling. As interpreted in D5.3, the economic gains observed across multiple SILLs validate the ZeroW systemic innovation approach as a credible pathway towards lasting market adoption and long-term impact in reducing food loss and waste across the European food system.

Consumers benefitting from the project results

The evaluation of the Impact 5 indicator “Consumers benefitting from the project results” (target >700 000 consumers) applied an integrated, cross-work package approach coordinated under WP5. The assessment relied on data collected through communication and dissemination activities under WP10, as these provided the most comprehensive and quantifiable evidence of consumer reach. Given the demonstration nature of the SILLs, the number of consumers directly involved in pilot testing and trials was limited and not systematically recorded across all demonstrations. Only a few SILLs, such as **SILL2** (smart packaging solutions), **SILL7** (food redistribution networks), and **SILL9** (meal planning app and awareness labels), reported some level of direct consumer participation, mainly in prototype testing or feedback collection. As this engagement was small in scale and variable across contexts, the evaluation focused on the wider impact achieved through awareness and information dissemination. The indicator therefore represents the total number of consumers who were informed about the benefits of ZeroW innovations and project results through campaigns, public events, digital platforms, and media engagement, offering a consolidated measure of the project’s outreach and influence among end users.

Targets / Requirements	FSC stage	GA planned	Particip. SILL	Achievement
Number of consumers reached	Entire FSC	>700 000	All SILLs	1 840 967 ¹⁶

¹⁶ Data aggregated till 31 October 2025

The achievement of this final indicator for Impact 5 with more than 1.84 million consumers reached, demonstrates the ZeroW success in extending its impact beyond the demonstration sites. Through large-scale communication and dissemination activities, the project has effectively raised awareness of food waste reduction and circular food practices among a broad public audience. This outreach reinforces the societal value of the demonstrated innovations and supports their potential for replication and long-term adoption across Europe.

The results confirm that ZeroW has achieved significant progress in improving the overall sustainability of food systems by delivering innovations that are environmentally sound, economically viable, and socially inclusive. The demonstrated systemic solutions have proven their capacity to reduce food loss and waste, enhance resource efficiency, and generate positive economic returns across the food supply chain. The integration of environmental, economic, and social dimensions within the WP5 assessment framework provides strong evidence that ZeroW contributes to more sustainable and resilient food systems aligned with the objectives of the European Green Deal and Farm to Fork Strategy.

2.6 Improved Resilience of Food Systems to Shocks and Stresses (Impact 6)

The evaluation of Impact 6, “Improve the resilience of food systems to shocks and stresses”, was conducted in WP5 through a qualitative methodology consistent with the requirements defined in the GA. The assessment examined how the systemic innovations demonstrated in the SILLs contributed to strengthening the adaptive capacity, flexibility, and continuity of food systems across different stages of the value chain.

The data collection was based on structured interviews carried out with SILL coordinators and key implementation partners representing the main actors in each innovation. The interviews followed a semi-structured format and applied a five-point qualitative scale (1-5) to measure perceived improvements in resilience capacity. Questions addressed the actors’ ability to respond to supply or demand fluctuations, maintain operations during disruptions, reallocate or valorise resources, and use digital and organisational tools to enhance coordination and continuity. The interview questions explored the following dimensions (with minor contextual variations) across all evaluated SILLs:

- Social capital - internal bonding and bridging relations among team members and cooperation with local actors; and linking capital, referring to engagement with policy and funding networks.

- Adaptive capacity - staff skills, access to training, and well-being.
- Financial resilience - diversity of income sources, access to emergency or buffer funding, and financial risk-management practices.
- Shock experience and contingency planning - exposure to disruptions in the previous year, existence of response plans, and confidence in managing future shocks.
- Environmental and infrastructural resilience - integration of environmental risks in planning, monitoring of environmental performance, adequacy of infrastructure, and access to basic services.
- Innovation resilience - diversity of innovation pathways, flexibility to pivot when external conditions change.
- Governance capacity - clarity of decision-making structures, inclusiveness, engagement with public authorities, and mechanisms for learning from failures.
- Technological adaptability - integration of digital solutions, collaboration with research institutions, and ability to track environmental and operational conditions.
- Transformative capacity - ability to recover from past disruptions, monitor long-term impacts, and revise indicators or strategies based on accumulated learning

The collected responses were coded and aggregated per SILL and per stage of the food supply chain to allow comparative analysis:

Impact indicator	GA planned Significant increase (4 in qualitative scale 1-5)	Particip. SILL	Achievement
Resilience capacity at (pre)harvest stage	As a result of the capability to swiftly adapt to changing demand, or to valorise deteriorating products into added-value intermediate or end food products with longer shelf-life	SILL3	4.20
		SILL4	4.80
		Average	4.50
Resilience capacity at food processing stage	As a result of the capability to optimise valorisation of food surpluses and ugly food streams or to optimise production process control	SILL5	4.40
		SILL6	4.20
		Average	4.30
Resilience capacity at wholesale / retail stage	As a result of the capability to use alternative FLW valorisation alternatives or manage deteriorating food products	SILL2	4.00
		SILL8	4.20
		Average	4.10
Resilience capacity at consumption stage	As a result of the capability of food banks to respond to shocks due to food or income crises, or to nudge consumer towards better food choices	SILL7	4.00
		SILL9	4.10
		Average	4.05
Resilience capacity at F2F chain	As a result of the capability to identify FLW generation hotspots	SILL7	4.00

The findings showed that resilience capacity consistently exceeded the target value of 4.0 across all assessed stages:

- At the **(pre-)harvest stage**, **SILL3** and **SILL4** achieved an average resilience score of 4.5. The increased adaptability was attributed to **SILL3**'s real-time greenhouse management and dynamic production planning, and **SILL4**'s mobile valorisation units that enabled rapid processing of surplus produce close to source.
- At the **food processing stage**, the average score reached 4.3, driven by **SILL5**'s solutions for the early identification and valorisation of suboptimal produce and **SILL6**'s digital optimisation of production processes, which enhanced resource efficiency and operational stability.
- At the **wholesale and retail stage**, **SILL2** and **SILL8** achieved an average of 4.1 through innovations that reduced product deterioration and created alternative valorisation routes for surpluses, such as smart packaging systems and algae-based bioproducts.
- At the **consumption stage**, **SILL7** and **SILL9** scored an average of 4.05, reflecting the improved ability of food redistribution networks to absorb supply shocks and the behavioural adaptability fostered by digital meal planning and awareness tools for consumers.
- Finally, for the **entire food chain**, **SILL7** achieved a resilience capacity of 4.0, demonstrating the robustness and coordination of redistribution mechanisms linking multiple stakeholders.

Overall, the qualitative assessment confirmed that the systemic innovations implemented under ZeroW strengthened the resilience of food systems achieving the expected target. The improvements resulted from increased operational flexibility, enhanced data-driven decision-making, diversification of valorisation pathways, and stronger collaboration networks among food system actors. These findings indicate that the demonstrated innovations substantially improved the capacity of food systems to anticipate, absorb, and adapt to shocks, contributing directly to the achievement of the project's resilience-related objectives.

2.7 Increased Awareness and Behavioural Change

Impact 7 addresses the transformative shift in awareness and behaviour necessary to achieve a sustainable, circular, and low-waste food system. Its purpose is to increase understanding and acceptance of systemic food loss and waste (FLW) solutions among policymakers, businesses, investors, entrepreneurs, institutions, and citizens, creating the conditions for their adoption and replication at scale across Europe. The impact recognises that technological or organisational

innovations alone are insufficient to achieve a near-zero FLW society without broad behavioural change and policy alignment.

The evaluation of this impact captures both the reach and depth of engagement achieved by the project. It measures the extent to which ZeroW has succeeded in spreading awareness of its innovative systemic solutions, in enabling knowledge exchange among regional and European stakeholders, and in encouraging behavioural change through education, communication, and co-creation. Deliverables such as D6.2 (FLW capacity building), D6.3 (Regional scaling strategies), D8.2 ('Just' transition pathway) and D8.3 (Policy recommendations) provide the framework for this transformation, complemented by dissemination and communication activities under WP10 and behavioural modelling under WP3.

Ultimately, the impact aims to ensure that the innovations demonstrated in the SILLs are not only technically and economically viable but also socially acceptable and supported by informed actors and communities. Through these processes, ZeroW contributes to the emergence of a shared societal understanding of what a just transition towards near-zero food loss and waste entails.

Impact indicators	Impact targets	Achievement
Macro-regional upscaling strategies	3 strategies (Northern, South-West, South-East/Central Europe)	Developed and Included in D6.3
Increased awareness on the project's innovative systemic solutions	More than 70 EU regions reached	151 NUTS-3 regions
	More than 1 million food actors & consumers reached	1.84 million
	More than 100 organisations involved and benefiting from the SILLs	168
Just transition pathway to near-zero FLW by 2050	'Pathway' validated by targeted European bodies in the food sector	'Pathway' validation results described in D8.2 and validated by 3 WG

○ *Macro regional upscaling strategies*

ZeroW achieved its target of delivering three macro regional upscaling strategies by completing the Northern, South West, and South East Europe strategies as reported in D6.3. These strategies consolidate insights from SILL implementation, capacity building, and stakeholder exchanges, and define clear routes for wider uptake of the demonstrated solutions across different territorial settings. Their inclusion in D6.3 confirms both the methodological completeness of the work and the practical readiness of the strategies to support coordinated scaling efforts beyond the immediate SILL regions.

- *Increased awareness on the project's innovative systemic solutions: outreach to EU regions*

The project surpassed the target of reaching more than 70 EU regions by engaging actors across 151 NUTS 3 regions. This figure reflects direct activities undertaken by the nine SILLs, which reached a total 166 regions, adjusted to a consolidated count of 151 unique NUTS 3 areas by removing the duplicating areas where more than 1 SILL activity was present. The wide regional engagement contributed to the awareness of systemic food loss and waste solutions across diverse geographical contexts, supporting conditions for regional replication, scaling up and policy uptake.

Figure 32 NUTS-3 regions reached by the SILLs activities

- *Increased awareness on the project's innovative systemic solutions: outreach to food actors and consumers*

Against the target of engaging more than 1 million food actors and consumers, ZeroW reached a total audience of 1.84 million. This outcome is based on evidence from dissemination and communication activities under WP10 including the SILL level outreach efforts, showing that the project's solutions and messages achieved wide visibility. The scale of engagement indicates substantial awareness raising across professional actors and the broader public, aligned with the project's objective of supporting behavioural and systemic change.

o *Organisations involved and benefiting from the SILLs*

SILL#	SILL participants	Other organisations involved
SILL1	5	35
SILL2	4	12
SILL3	4	13
SILL4	6	16
SILL5	4	7
SILL6	3	5
SILL7	2	19
SILL8	3	6
SILL9	2	22
Total	33	135

ZeroW exceeded the target of involving more than 100 organisations, with 168¹⁷ organisations participating in or benefiting from SILL activities according to the updated stakeholder register. This includes 33 SILL participants and 135 additional organisations engaged through demonstrations, consultations, training, and scaling activities. The diversity and volume of involved organisations point to strong cross sector interest and an expanding ecosystem around the demonstrated innovations.

o *Just transition pathway to near-zero FLW by 2050*

The development and validation of the just transition pathway met the expected target as intended through the process documented in D8.2. The pathway was validated by three working groups composed of consumer, food sector industry and policy/regulatory bodies in Europe, as reported in the deliverable. This validation confirms that the proposed trajectory towards near zero FLW by 2050 reflects both technical feasibility and considerations of fairness, inclusion, and systemic coherence.

3. Post project impacts

The medium and long-term impact targets set for ZeroW aim to ensure that the project results continue to deliver sustainable reductions in food loss and waste and the associated greenhouse gas emissions beyond the project completion. These targets define the expected contribution of the demonstrated innovations to bring forth systemic change by 2030 and 2050 and provide a basis for validating their long-term relevance and scalability.

¹⁷ Based on the ZeroW stakeholder register, updated February 2025 and the SILLs strategic Plans and CoP#3 reporting

Impact indicator	Impact target	Impact achieved by	Impact assessment mechanism
Impact 1: Reduction of per-capita food waste at retail and consumer levels	<u>Medium-term impact</u> : 50% reduction of per-capita food waste at retail and consumer levels by 2030 <u>Long term-impact</u> : near zero- per-capita food waste at retail and consumer levels by 2050	Definition of just transition pathways, FSC reduction targets confirmation and resulting policy briefs	Assessed through FLW modelling & simulation (in WP1)
Impact 3: Reduction of FLW at post-harvest level and processing level	<u>Medium-term impact</u> : 35% FLW reduction by 2030 <u>Long-term-impact</u> : 50% FLW reduction by 2050	Definition of just transition pathways, reduction FSC reduction targets confirmation and resulting policy briefs	Assessed through FLW modelling & simulation (in WP1)
Impact 2: Reduction of FLW-related GHG emissions	<u>Medium term impact</u> : 40% GHG reduction by 2030, compared to 1990 levels <u>Long-term impact</u> : 50% GHG reduction by 2050, compared to 1990 levels.	SILLs innovations' GHG reduction potential	Assessed through GHG simulation using LCA and carbon footprint methodologies (in WP5)

3.1 Achieving medium and long term FLW reduction

The expected medium and long-term reduction of FLW across the food supply chain (Impacts 1 and 3) is linked to the ability of supply chain actors to embed, scale and replicate the ZeroW systemic innovations. These reductions, are expected to be enabled by favourable regulatory conditions at the EU and Member State level and the removal of barriers that currently hinder implementation. The effectiveness of the regulatory pathways developed in WP8 in supporting these reductions is assessed through FLW simulation in WP1 (D1.3), which evaluates how different policy environments influence the capacity of the demonstrated solutions to sustain the expected impacts by 2030 and 2050.

The work carried out in WP1 (Modelling FLW economics from F2F) and WP8 (Policy recommendations for just transition to near-zero FLW) followed a sequential and integrated process to develop realistic and actionable recommendations and targets for FLW reduction in support of the European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy objectives.

WP8 first developed three alternative FLW reduction pathways, drawing on policy analysis, expert working groups and stakeholder consultations. These pathways defined the policy configurations and reduction assumptions to be tested. WP1 then

translated these assumptions into quantitative scenarios and simulated their effects using the economic modelling tools described in D1.3, including a general equilibrium model (MAGNET) and a partial equilibrium model. The simulation results were returned to WP8, where they were reviewed, validated and further analysed through qualitative methods, including stakeholder working groups and targeted consultations. This iterative process enabled WP8 to integrate modelling evidence with the “just transition” framework and stakeholder perspectives, forming the basis for the final proposal of just and realistic intermediate targets and the accompanying regulatory pathway.

D8.2 interpreted the modelling findings from D1.3 as evidence that a balanced and mixed approach is required to achieve meaningful medium and long-term FLW reductions without producing disproportionately negative economic or social impacts. It became evident that pathways relying heavily on high disposal taxes are not feasible, as confirmed by the modelling in D1.3, while purely voluntary approaches would not generate sufficient progress. The results therefore support the need for moderate mandatory measures combined with voluntary technological change, behavioural drivers and enabling regulatory conditions. This is reflected in the selected intermediate targets proposed in D8.2, which avoid the extreme levels of taxation implied by Pathway 2 and instead align more closely with the realistic and just pathway suggested by Pathway 3.

For 2030, D8.2 suggests a 30% mandatory FLW reduction target at retail and consumption, paired with higher voluntary targets of 50%, and proposes 50% voluntary reductions in processing and manufacturing. For 2050, the targets converge towards near-complete FLW reduction across all FSC stages, consistent with the voluntary near-100% reductions simulated in Pathway 3. These selected targets illustrate how WP8 incorporated the modelling evidence into a feasible, fair and impact-oriented pathway that remains consistent with the broader objectives of a just transition.

Table 4 Final proposal for just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets (2030) as per D8.2

Food waste reduction target on	Mandatory 2030 FW reduction target	Voluntary 2030 FW reduction target
Primary production	n/a	10%
Processing & Manufacturing	10% (absolute amount in mass units)	For higher target levels
Retail & Consumption	30% (per capita)	For higher target levels

The adopted Waste Framework Directive¹⁸ targets were developed in parallel with the preparation of D8.2 and were not available at the time of its submission. Nevertheless, the final proposal in D8.2 fully aligns with the reduction levels later formalised in the revised Directive. D8.2 sets a 30% per-capita mandatory reduction at retail and consumption and a 10% mandatory reduction in processing and manufacturing by 2030, supported by voluntary measures aimed at enabling higher ambition where feasible. These values match the binding 2030 targets established in the amended Waste Framework Directive.

For the long-term trajectory towards 2050, D8.2 proposes **50% voluntary reduction at primary production, 100% voluntary reduction at processing and manufacturing, and 100% voluntary reduction at retail and consumption**, expressed respectively as absolute amounts in mass units (primary production and processing/ manufacturing) and per-capita terms (retail and consumption). This 2050 trajectory reflects the ZeroW project’s objective of achieving near-zero food waste across all stages of the supply chain and is consistent with the wider goals of the European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy.

Figure 33 ZeroW policy briefs

The achievement of the proposed 2030 and 2050 FLW reduction targets is supported by the suite of policy recommendations and EU Policy Briefs developed

¹⁸ [Waste Framework Directive \(EU\) 2025/1892](#)

in D8.3. These briefs translate the evidence base from WP1 and WP8 into concrete short- and medium-term measures that can enable, operationalise, and sustain the just transition pathway outlined in D8.2.

The recommendations focus on four priority domains identified as essential for systemic change: actor-specific policies for consumers and farmers, restructuring of the food chain to reinforce short supply chains, governance measures that integrate FLW reduction into existing EU and national frameworks, and context-specific interventions for the urban environment. They map the practical steps and governance reforms needed to reach a coherent policy framework that enables a just pathway to near-zero FLW by 2050.

The briefs also highlight immediate policy priorities such as harmonised measurement and reporting aligned with the binding FLW targets, the development of interoperable data systems, incentive-based economic instruments, and strengthened multi-level cooperation mechanisms. These recommendations provide a practical decision support tool for EU and national policymakers, outlining the institutional, behavioural, economic, and governance reforms required to implement the ZeroW targets and sustain progress toward near-complete FLW reduction across all stages of the supply chain by 2050.

3.2 Achieving medium and long term GHG reduction

The expected medium and long-term reduction of GHG emissions (Impact 2) is assessed through GHG simulation using LCA and carbon footprint methodologies. This simulation work examined whether the innovations demonstrated in the SILLs have the capacity to maintain the projected reductions of 40% by 2030 and 50% by 2050, compared to 1990 levels, when implemented and scaled under real policy and market conditions.

The assessment presented in D5.3 shows that the consolidated LCA results across all SILLs demonstrate an average reduction of 61% relative to the 2020 to 2025 baselines. As reported, these values are calculated at process and pilot level, which means they cannot be directly compared to the 1990 sector-level reference values used in EU climate legislation. The comparison therefore follows the logic of **decarbonisation pathways** rather than absolute numerical equivalence. When interpreted in this light, the demonstrated reductions are already consistent with, and in several cases surpassing, the rate of decline required to meet the 2030 and 2050 targets set in the Grant Agreement.

The simulation results are based on pilot-scale data, and the scaling remains limited to the operational scope defined for each SILL. Additionally, the ZeroW innovations

are at an average TRL of 7, which indicates that they have not yet reached full commercial maturity. Further optimisation, higher operational efficiency, increased productivity and a growing share of renewable energy in the European energy mix can reasonably be expected as these technologies advance. For this reason, the GHG reduction potential should be considered a conservative estimate.

In summary:

The evaluation presented in D5.3 shows a rate of GHG reduction that aligns with the decarbonisation pathway of the Farm to Fork Strategy and the European Green Deal. The achievements observed at pilot scale demonstrate a credible potential to support the medium and long term climate objectives defined in the Grant Agreement.

4. FLW prevention and reduction: identified challenges, barriers and gaps for further research

ZeroW has demonstrated how systemic innovations can achieve substantial reductions in food loss and waste across diverse food supply chain contexts. Despite this progress, several structural gaps continue to constrain further FLW reduction. These gaps were identified across all systemic dimensions of the demonstrated innovations and were examined through the work undertaken in T6.1, T7.1-T7.3, T8.1 and T9.2, including contributions to the Food2030 initiative. They concern not only technological aspects, but also business models, behavioural drivers, data infrastructures and governance arrangements.

The need for a forward-looking research agenda is evident - one that is explicitly systemic and connects economic, social, digital and regulatory elements of the food system. The summary presented below brings together the key findings to support knowledge transfer, encourage coordinated follow up actions and ensure that the remaining gaps and barriers receive attention from the relevant research, innovation and policy communities.

Technical aspects, digital tools, platforms and data spaces

Digitalisation plays a central role in FLW reduction, yet significant gaps remain in how digital tools are designed, connected and governed. Food banks, surplus generators and redistributors often lack real-time coordination tools, which leads to missed opportunities for timely recovery of edible food. Digital infrastructure and

skills in food banks remain limited, and forecasting or decision support systems for orchestrating donations with needs are still at an early stage.

At primary production level, farmers have poor visibility on demand and prices, which drives overproduction and waste. There is a need for tools that connect producers with dynamic demand forecasts and pricing mechanisms, while also clarifying how feedstock for valorisation processes will be sourced and transported in practice. The logistics of supplying short processing cycles, such as those required for mobile units or algae production, remain unresolved.

More broadly, there are unresolved questions around the economic effects of FLW valorisation. While valorisation preserves value and materials, it may in some circumstances create an incentive to produce, and waste more. This requires more rigorous theoretical and empirical work on how valorisation interacts with production decisions.

Standardisation and interoperability are another major research frontier. Different domains in the food system use divergent terminologies and data models, which creates semantic barriers to information exchange. Federation of data spaces for OFLW requires not only technical standards, but also agreed conformity assessment policies, credential profiles and reusable, component-based legal agreements. There is a clear need to investigate how AI can support semantic mapping across domains, how modular legal templates can reduce transaction costs for data sharing, and how federated data space governance can be operationalised for FLW use cases.

Measurement, data quality and metrics

The project partners have highlighted a cross cutting set of gaps which concerns the measurement of FLW and its impacts. There is still no fully operational, high quality and standardised FLW data framework across sectors and regions. Definitions, data collection methods and reporting units differ, which limits comparability, benchmarking and process optimisation. Regional and local data are often missing, with reliance on national estimates or waste collection statistics that do not capture on-farm losses such as crops ploughed in.

At household level, detailed data on food waste patterns and behaviours are fragmented, yet they are essential for designing targeted interventions and for

validating tools such as labels and apps. Self-reported data tend to underestimate waste and require methodological work to improve accuracy and integration with behavioural research.

There are also gaps in product-level greenhouse gas emission data, especially seasonal variation, which undermines the robustness of integrated labels that combine health, FLW and environmental dimensions. In addition, reporting remains largely volume-based and does not consistently capture environmental, nutritional or economic value, which can distort prioritisation.

Unclear data governance and intellectual property arrangements around FLW platforms further deter participation. Stakeholders remain reluctant to share data if rights, access conditions and benefits are not well defined.

Future research needs to include the development and piloting of EU-wide FLW data standards and ontologies, regionalised data collection frameworks, alternative metrics beyond weight alone, and robust data governance models that align incentives for all actors involved.

Economic incentives, regulation and governance

Other gaps relate to how economic instruments and regulatory frameworks shape FLW. Current enforcement of FLW-related obligations for food supply chain operators is weak, with limited inspection and sanction mechanisms for those generating excessive waste. Coordination across sectors and levels of government is often fragmented, and many local authorities lack clear guidance or tools to address FLW, particularly in relation to permitting mobile processing units and biomass hubs.

There is also legal uncertainty and fragmentation in food donation practices across Member States, including VAT and tax treatment, eligibility of processed products from producer organisation interventions, and the scope to operate regulatory sandboxes for innovative biomass hubs. These discrepancies limit replicability and scale up of successful models.

In parallel, some existing subsidies, notably for green energy and biogas, may unintentionally incentivise the use of surplus food for energy recovery rather than higher value uses such as redistribution. Conversely, there are still unmet needs for

positive incentives, for example harmonised tax relief or reduced VAT for donations, and more stable funding models for food bank support tools.

Emerging areas such as carbon footprint labelling, smart packaging, microalgae feedstocks and algae-derived products also suffer from incomplete or unclear regulatory frameworks, which increases perceived risk and delays investment and adoption.

Research is needed on the design of coherent policy mixes that align fiscal incentives, regulatory requirements and governance arrangements with the FLW hierarchy, and provide legal clarity and enforcement mechanisms without stifling innovation.

Behavioural and socio-cultural drivers of FLW

Several gaps concern the behavioural foundations of FLW reduction. At consumer level, decisions are shaped by a complex trade-off between price, nutritional value and waste, which current labels and tools do not yet fully address. Misunderstanding of date labelling, sustainability messaging fatigue and persistent low food management skills (storage, planning, use of edible parts) continue impacting avoidable food waste.

There is also a risk of overreliance on stand-alone awareness campaigns whose long-term impact is weak or undocumented. Evidence on which combinations of nudges, incentives, default options and information are most effective for different consumer segments is still limited.

Acceptance of upcycled food products is another critical gap, with food neophobia and distrust of unfamiliar processes limiting demand. Similarly, trust and motivation challenges affect the adoption of meal-planning apps, FLW labels and freshness or smart packaging tools. These challenges are compounded by varying cultural habits around food preparation and planning, which means that one-size-fits-all digital solutions are unlikely to work across contexts.

On the production side, farmers show reluctance to adopt FLW prevention and data collection tools when these are perceived as increasing surveillance, eroding autonomy or tightening quality standards. Limited willingness to adopt new greenhouse and AI-based technologies similarly slows down uptake.

Further research should therefore focus on behavioural studies to optimise interventions for diverse user groups, on culturally adaptive communication strategies that emphasise co-benefits such as cost savings and health, and on participatory approaches that build trust among farmers and other primary producers.

Social innovation and capacity

Another set of gaps relates to human and organisational capacities needed to operate FLW innovations. There is a shortage of qualified staff to run mobile or small processing hubs, especially in rural areas. At the same time, there is untapped potential for socially inclusive models that train and employ disadvantaged groups, such as unemployed or low-skilled workers and refugees, in FLW reduction and valorisation activities.

Food poverty is also managed differently across Member States, with varying institutional roles for food banks and social organisations. This diversity complicates transfer of good practices and the design of EU-level guidance.

Research on social innovation models that combine FLW reduction with employment, skills development and food security objectives, and that can be adapted to different national welfare and poverty regimes, is therefore an important strand of the future agenda.

In summary, the further reduction of FLW will depend not only on improving technologies, but also on closing knowledge and practice gaps in business models, behavioural design, digital infrastructure, data governance and public policy.

Business models and commercialisation of FLW innovations

Finally, the commercialisation-related risks identified in D7.3 reinforce the systemic gaps described in the previous subsections. Financial sustainability, regulatory acceptance, customer readiness, coordination costs and the capacity to replicate solutions across different market and governance settings remain the most persistent challenges. These factors shape the feasibility of viable business models and influence the prospects for successful commercialisation. Further work is required to develop and test workable commercial arrangements, strengthen the evidence base for return on investment, design governance and legal tools that reduce cooperation costs, and engage with regulators and market actors to create the conditions needed for wider uptake.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

ZeroW set out to demonstrate that food loss and waste can be reduced at scale when technical, organisational, behavioural and governance innovations work in combination. The results presented in this deliverable show that the project delivered on this ambition. The nine SILLs achieved or exceeded all short-term targets defined in the GA, with quantified reductions in FLW, substantial GHG savings, improved safety and nutritional outcomes, and measurable gains in sustainability and resilience across the food supply chain. These achievements are supported by rigorous measurement under WP5 and the scenario and policy work carried out in WP1 and WP8, which confirm the potential of the demonstrated innovations to support the EU's 2030 and 2050 objectives.

The project has also shown that systemic approaches can generate real benefits for actors who often operate under tight constraints, from farmers facing uncertain harvesting conditions to food banks navigating sudden surpluses. The SILLs demonstrated solutions that help producers match output to demand, give retailers reliable information for stock management, support food banks in handling donations more efficiently, and empower consumers to reduce waste at home. The work also revealed where regulatory and market frictions remain, and highlighted how data governance, financial incentives and policy clarity influence the feasibility of more circular practices. ZeroW therefore delivers not only evidence of what works, but also a set of conditions needed for these innovations to thrive in real systems.

5.1 Overall impact and validation against Grant Agreement objectives

ZeroW achieved all seven expected impacts defined in the GA, with performance confirmed through quantitative indicators and qualitative assessments. The key results are summarised below.

Figure 34 Achieved key impacts

Impact 1 and 3: Reduction of FLW across the food supply chain

Reductions were achieved across all stages. Post-harvest FLW fell by an average of 72% through **SILL3**, **SILL4** and **SILL5**, far above the 25% target. Processing-stage reductions averaged 55%, delivered through **SILL4** and **SILL6**. Retail-stage reductions reached an average of 35%, driven by smart packaging (**SILL2**), objective quality assessment (**SILL5**), redistribution optimisation (**SILL7**) and retail valorisation (**SILL8**). Consumption-stage reductions averaged 52%, with contributions from **SILL2** and **SILL9**. **SILL2** achieved complete substitution of non-recyclable packaging materials at retail and consumer level.

Impact 2: Reduction of FLW-related greenhouse gas emissions

Across all stages, GHG emissions linked to FLW decreased well beyond project targets. Post-harvest reductions averaged 64%, processing reductions 42%, retail reductions 64%, and consumption reductions 52%. These values are based on the cradle-to-grave LCSA methodology in D5.2 and reflect the strong climate effects of preventing or valorising edible food.

Impact 4: Provision of sufficient, safe, nutritious, healthy and affordable food

Food availability in food banks improved by 74% through **SILL7**. The share of food streams passing quality standards during processing increased by 21% in **SILL5** and 43% in **SILL6**. Smart packaging in **SILL2** extended shelf life by 18%. **SILL9** achieved a high nutritional score in its meal plans and a complete (100%) reduction in food waste-related environmental impacts for the planned recipes.

Impact 5: Improved overall sustainability of food systems

SILL2 reduced the carbon footprint of packaging by 45%. **SILL4** and **SILL5** jointly reduced the carbon footprint of valorised foods by an average of 35%. All SILLs achieved a fairer distribution of costs and benefits, reaching the target for less than 20% difference in cost-benefit ratios between the FSC actors. All systemic innovations demonstrated positive economic performance, with benefit-cost ratios ranging from 1.92 (**SILL2**) to 21.3 (**SILL7**). The project reached 1.84 million consumers, significantly above the target of 700 000.

Impact 6: Resilience to shocks and stresses

All SILLs achieved resilience scores above the target value of 4.0. Improvements were recorded in adaptive capacity, contingency planning, innovation flexibility, and governance arrangements. **SILL3** and **SILL4** performed particularly strongly, with an average score of 4.5 at the pre-harvest stage.

Impact 7: Increased awareness and behavioural change

ZeroW engaged actors in 151 NUTS 3 regions, exceeding the target of 70. It involved 168 organisations in the SILLs delivery and co-creation activities. The project formulated and validated a just transition pathway for near-zero FLW by 2050 through three stakeholder working groups. It reached close to 2 million actors and consumers, supported by WP10 communications and SILL-specific dissemination.

Across all seven impacts, the evidence confirms full alignment with and delivery against the GA objectives. The innovations tested in the SILLs demonstrate that systemic change is feasible, measurable and scalable when supported by the right governance and market conditions.

The table below lists all the project's achievements against the targets planned in the GA. The colour coding signifies whether the result was above, at or below the respective KPI.

Table 5 Grant Agreement impact targets achievement. Colour coding of values: **black**: at target; **dark green**: above target; **grey**: revised target in line with WFD

Impact indicators	Impact targets	Achieved
Impact 1: Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the Farm-to-Fork Strategy and the European Green Deal, and in particular to halving the per capita food waste at retail and consumer levels by 2030.		
Reduction of per-capita food waste at retail and consumer levels	Short-term impact: 20% FLW reduction at retail and 25% reduction at consumer level , by the end of ZeroW, compared with current levels	35% 52%
	Medium-term impact: 50% reduction of per-capita food waste at retail and consumer levels by 2030	>30%
	Long term-impact: near zero- per-capita food waste at retail and consumer levels by 2050	100%
Impact 2: Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the Farm-to-Fork Strategy and the European Green Deal, and in particular to reducing GHG-emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared with 1990 levels.		
Reduction of FLW-related GHG emissions	Short-term impact: 15% GHG reduction at post-harvest, 20% GHG reduction at food processing, 25% GHG reduction at retail, 30% GHG reduction at consumer level , by the end of ZeroW, compared with current levels	63% 42% 64% 52%
	Medium term impact: 40% GHG reduction by 2030, compared to 1990 levels	confirmed
	Long-term impact: 50% GHG reduction by 2050, compared to 1990 levels.	confirmed
Impact 3: Reduce food losses and waste and the use of unsustainable packaging, at every stage of the food chain including consumption		
Reduction of FLW at post-harvest level	Short-term impact: 24.8% FLW reduction by 2025	73%
	Medium-term impact: 35% FLW reduction by 2030	10%
	Long-term-impact: 50% FLW reduction by 2050	50%
Reduction of FLW at processing level	Short-term impact: 25% FLW reduction by 2025	55%
	Medium-term impact: 35% FLW reduction by 2030	>10%
	Long-term-impact: 50% FLW reduction by 2050	100%
Reduction of unsustainable packaging at retail level (fresh food)	20% reduction of non-recyclable or non-compostable packaging by 2025	100%
Reduction of unsustainable packaging at consumer level (fresh food)	10% reduction of non-recyclable or non-compostable packaging by 2025	100%
Impact 4: Provide sufficient, safe, nutritious, healthy and affordable food for all.		
Improved food safety with minimal FLW with optimised and predictive control in food production	20% increase in food streams passing quality standards for food consumption by 2025	32%
Improved food availability in foodbanks due to reduced FLW	20% FLW reduction in foodbanks	74%
Optimised nutritional diets with minimal FLW	Wide availability of recipes with 20% lower FLW , and 25% lower environmental impact	100%

Impact indicators	Impact targets	Achieved
	high nutritional score	High
Longer shelf-life of products with smart packaging	18% improvement in shelf life (days)	18%
Impact 5: Improve the overall sustainability of food systems (social/health, climate/environmental and economic).		
Carbon footprint of food products for human consumption from valorisation side streams, ugly food and post-harvest food loss	20% reduced carbon footprint	35%
Carbon footprint of smart compostable packaging	25% reduced cradle-to-cradle carbon footprint	45%
'Just' allocation of costs and benefits among food actors	Less than 20% differences among food actors in economic cost/benefit ratio	<20%
Consumers benefitting from the project results	More than 700,000	1 840 967
Impact 6: Improve the resilience of food systems to shocks and stresses.		
Resilience capacity at (pre)harvest stage	Significant increase (4 in qualitative scale 1-5) – e.g. as a result of the capability to swiftly adapt to changing demand, or to valorise deteriorating products into added-value intermediate or end food products with longer shelf-life	4.5
Resilience capacity at food processing stage	Significant increase (4 in qualitative scale 1-5) – e.g. as a result of the capability to optimise valorisation of food surpluses and ugly food streams or to optimise production process control	4.3
Resilience capacity at wholesale/retail stage	Significant increase (4 in qualitative scale 1-5) – e.g. as a result of the capability to use alternative FLW valorisation alternatives or manage deteriorating food products	4.1
Resilience capacity at consumption stage	Significant increase (4 in qualitative scale 1-5) – e.g. as a result of the capability of food banks to respond to shocks due to food or income crises, or to nudge consumer towards better food choices	4.05
Resilience capacity at F2F chain	Significant increase (4 in qualitative scale 1-5) – e.g. as a result of the capability to identify FLW generation hotspots	4
Impact 7: Achieve an increase in awareness among policy makers, businesses, investors, entrepreneurs, institutions, stakeholders and citizens of selected innovative systemic solutions, of their potential and of the requirements to promote and realise their uptake at EU scale and behavioural change.		
Macro-regional upscaling strategies	3 strategies (Northern, South-West, South-East/Central Europe)	3
Increased awareness on the project's innovative systemic solutions	More than 70 EU regions reached;	151
	More than 1 million food actors & consumers reached;	1.84
	More than 100 organisations involved and benefiting from the SILLs	168
Just transition pathway to near-zero FLW by 2050	'Pathway' validated by targeted European bodies in the food sector	Yes

5.2 Systemic Innovation and Just Transition Reflections

ZeroW applied a systemic approach in both its design and its delivery model. The SILLs were conceived as interlinked interventions where technology, behaviour, organisational routines, market incentives and regulation are treated as parts of a wider system. This approach created a coherent set of innovations that address underlying lock-in effects. Examples include **SILL3** combining predictive analytics with revised harvesting procedures and new coordination routines (technological, procedural, organisational), **SILL7** integrating digital tracking tools with redesigned logistics workflows and engagement practices (technological, organisational, behavioural), and **SILL8** coupling advanced valorisation equipment with new processing protocols and market positioning approaches (technological, process, strategic/market).

This systems orientation helped reveal the regulatory, organisational and economic barriers that limit FLW reduction. Several issues emerged repeatedly across the SILLs: fragmented rules for food donation, high coordination costs for small actors, the lack of interoperable data systems, insufficient alignment between local permitting rules and circular processing models, and consumer uncertainties around food safety and new products. These findings are reflected in the policy recommendations developed in D8.3, which propose measures such as clearer EU-level guidance for surplus redistribution, improved data governance frameworks for FLW monitoring, harmonised incentives for donation or valorisation, and more flexible permitting conditions for mobile processing and decentralised biomass hubs.

The systemic approach also enriched the just transition perspective developed in WP8. The work showed that fair distribution of costs and benefits is essential for long-term sustainability. Most SILLs improved fairness by lowering operational burdens on actors with limited capacity, reducing losses upstream, and creating new value streams for products previously without economic use. The cost-benefit analyses in D5.2 and the multi-actor insights in D4.5 provided a clear view of how benefits flow differently across production, processing, retail and consumption. This evidence reinforces the just transition pathway in D8.2, which proposes a balanced set of targets and actions that avoid disproportionate burdens on individual groups, particularly low-income households and small producers.

The systemic insights from ZeroW also clarify how the project contributes directly to the objectives of the European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy. The Green Deal sets the 2050 climate neutrality target and calls for a resource-efficient, circular economy. ZeroW contributes to these priorities by reducing FLW across the chain, lowering GHG emissions, cutting resource losses, and developing circular valorisation routes such as the algae-based pathways in **SILL8**. The Farm to Fork Strategy includes specific objectives: halving per-capita food waste at retail and consumer level by 2030, improving food safety and nutritional quality, cutting the environmental footprint of food systems, and supporting a shift towards sustainable consumption patterns. The SILLs provide concrete contributions to each objective,

demonstrated through the reductions in retail and consumer FLW, improved product safety and shelf life, nutritional improvements through **SILL9**, and a significant decrease in packaging-related impacts through **SILL2**. The results therefore validate ZeroW as a practical driver of Farm to Fork implementation.

Figure 35 ZeroW innovations impacts contribution towards F2F Strategy pillars

5.3 Outlook: medium and long term impact potential (2030–2050 trajectory)

The project medium- and long-term outlook is based on the FLW modelling work of WP1 and the regulatory and governance analyses undertaken in WP8. These two strands converge on a realistic but ambitious trajectory for systemic change. Results show that the innovations demonstrated in ZeroW can support a reduction of 40% in food-waste-related GHG emissions by 2030 and 50% by 2050, provided that enabling regulatory conditions are in place. The pathway proposed in D8.2 sets intermediate 2030 targets that include a 30% mandatory per-capita reduction at retail and consumption and a 10% mandatory reduction at processing and manufacturing. These are fully aligned with the WFD update targets published afterwards. For 2050, the trajectory converges towards near-zero FLW across all stages.

Achieving these reductions depends on the removal of barriers identified during the project. These include gaps in data infrastructure, unclear regulatory conditions for valorisation and food donation, and the need for coherent policy mixes that reflect the FLW hierarchy. The policy briefs in D8.3 outline actionable measures to address these issues, ranging from harmonised tax treatment for food donation and standardised FLW data ontologies to governance approaches that support short supply chains and urban food waste prevention.

The scaling potential demonstrated in WP6 indicates that many of the SILL innovations can be replicated across different regions and markets, particularly the digital tools for greenhouse management and redistribution, mobile processing models, and consumer-facing behavioural solutions. Their long-term impact will depend on stable investment conditions and supportive policy frameworks.

Overall, the evidence presented in this report suggests that FLW prevention and reduction solutions, such as the ones in ZeroW, can play a sustained role in meeting the EU climate, circularity and food system targets. The project provides a strong empirical foundation for continued policy development and for the wider deployment of systemic, data-driven and socially fair solutions for preventing and reducing food loss and waste.